

EOSC: Landscaping analysis

Main Authors:	Daria Forlenza and Andrea Tregua (T6 Ecosystems)
Contributing Authors:	Federica Tanlongo, Biljana Kosanovic, Eleni Toli, Valentino Cavalli, Ludek Matyska, Per-Olov Hammargren
Editors:	Antonella Passani, Simona De Rosa and Andrea Nicolai (T6 Ecosystems)
Acknowledgements:	The authors wish to thank the teams of EOSC-Pillar, NI4OS-Europe, EOSC-Nordic and EOSC-Synergy: without their support and collaboration this report would have been impossible.
Version:	1.0
Abstract:	This deliverable provides an overview of the Open Science landscape in 35 countries. It is based on the data gathered by four EU-funded regional projects (EOSC-Pillar, NI4OS-Europe, EOSC-Nordic and EOSC-Synergy) that have been re-elaborated to offer a European overview.

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List of Terms and Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Definition
Ab. Val.	Absolute Value
API	Application Programming Interface
BEIS	Department for Business, Energy and Industrial Strategy
BSC	Barcelona Supercomputing Centre
CDI	Collaborative Data Infrastructures
CESSDA	Consortium of European Social Science Data Archive
CINECA	Italian Consortium Computing Centre
CSIC	Spanish National Research Council
DARIAH	Digital research infrastructures for Art and Humanities
DHI	Digital Innovation Hub
ECI	European Cloud Initiatives
EMBL	European Molecular Biology Laboratory
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
EGI Federation	European Grid Initiative Federation
ESFRI	European Strategy Forum on research infrastructures
ETH	Swiss Federal Institute of Technology
EuroHPC	European Supercomputing Research Network
FAIRsFAIR	Fostering Fair Data Practices in Europe
FAIR	Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability and Reusability
GCS	Gauss Centre for SuperComputing
GENTI	French National High Performance Computing Organization
HELG	High Level Expert Group European Open Science Cloud
HPC	High-Performance Computing
IdP	Identity Provider
KPIs	Key Performance Indicators
LUMI	Large Unified Modern Infrastructure
NOADs	National Open Access Desks
NORDUnet	Nordic Gateway for Research & Education
NREN	National Research and Education Network
OA	Open Access
OS	Open Science
PRACE	Partnership for Advanced Computing in Europe
SMEs	Medium-Sized Enterprises
SLAs	Service Level Agreements
SRIA	The Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda
RDA	Research Data Alliance
RDM	Research Data Management
UKRI	United Kingdom Research and Innovation Organization

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Executive Summary

This report provides an overview on Open Science actors, practices and policies at European level and beyond with the aim of supporting the EOSC governance board to take informed decisions in the design and implementation of EOSC.

EOSC aims at making research data in Europe accessible to all researchers under the same terms of use and distribution, encouraging a culture of open research data and FAIR principles. It is the result of a long quest for innovation and collaboration started many years ago.

This report maps the point of view and ongoing practices of EOSC-relevant stakeholders in 35 countries, analysing their familiarity with EOSC and Open Science principles. It also gathers information on the services they provide, on user communities and on policies in place.

The analysis presented here integrates results of several surveys and data gathering activities carried out by four EU-funded regional projects: EOSC-Pillar, NI4OS-Europe, EOSC-Nordic and EOSC-Synergy. Representatives of 30 countries have been reached through online surveys, while five additional countries have been analysed through desk research and secondary data analysis. Information was collected and elaborated in different moments between September 2019 and June 2020.

The analysis is exploratory and descriptive in nature and does not provide a statistically representative view of the situation at the European or country level. Nevertheless, it shows some trends on the situation of Open Science achievements and next steps. Stakeholders in the survey represent research organisations, universities, research infrastructures, e-infrastructures, funding bodies, representatives of the user's communities including those of the private sector and initiatives active as facilitators or promoters of Open Science principle and practices. The stakeholders' typologies surveyed by the four regional projects vary in order to better reflect the actors active in the countries under analysis.

Considering the results of the analysis carried out, it is possible to say that the majority of respondents are familiar with EOSC and consider it as potentially beneficial for their organisation. The capability to contribute to EOSC differs from country to country with countries such as Italy, Austria, Belgium, Germany and France more likely to contribute than others such as Moldova, Serbia and North Macedonia which started to develop Open Science policies more recently.

Considering the Open Science services offered, there is a prevalence of services targeting natural sciences, followed by engineering and technology.

Researchers (both from university and non) and students are the main users of research infrastructures' and e-infrastructures' services, but access, in the majority of cases, is granted to other user groups. The great majority of service providers participating in the surveys offer training to their users.

More than half of the respondents of the countries included in the survey show that the sustainability model of research infrastructures and e-infrastructures is based on public funding: which are granted in most cases by governmental and European funds. Nevertheless, one third of respondents declared to have other sources of funding such as revenues-based services, consultancy and online services offering.

The data gathered both through surveys and desk research show that there is a convergence towards EOSC as a “principle” and as a community. In some countries, the actual convergence at technical and policy/regulation level appears eased by the presence of standardised working regulations, technical solutions (API provision) and Service Level Agreements (LSAs.)

1 Introduction

This report provides an overview on Open Science actors, practices and policies at European level, and beyond, with the aim of supporting the EOSC governance board to take informed decisions in the future design and implementation of EOSC.

More specifically, this report maps EOSC-relevant stakeholders in 35 countries, analysing their familiarity with EOSC and Open Science principles and gathers information on the services they provide, on user communities they serve and on policies in place.

The analysis presented here integrates results of several surveys and data gathering activities carried out by four EU-funded regional projects: EOSC-Pillar¹, NI4OS-Europe², EOSC-Nordic³ and EOSC-Synergy⁴.

The report is structured as follows:

- **Chapter 1** sets the scene of this report summarizing the process carried out at European level for the promotion of Open Science and the initiatives that are now leading the research community towards EOSC.
- **Chapter 2** describes the methodological approach followed for the analysis presented in the following chapters including the data gathering and analysis approach.
- **Chapters from 3 to 6** are dedicated to the analysis of the data.
- **Chapter 7** concludes the report.

1.1 Setting the ground for the landscaping: background analysis

Between July and September 2014, the European Commission conducted a public consultation on Science 2.0. ‘Science 2.0’ describes an on-going evolution in ways of doing and organising research. These changes are enabled by digital technologies and they are driven by globalisation and growth of the scientific community as well as the need to address the challenges of our time⁵. The results of the consultation suggested that many stakeholders preferred using an alternative term to ‘Science 2.0’ which was ‘Open Science’. Indeed, it appeared to be the most popular alternative term.

Among the policy actions identified in the consultation, one was to “*Develop research infrastructures for Open Science*” and to “*Enable big data solutions in secured virtual environments to generate smart solutions*”

¹ EOSC-Pillar. <https://www.eosc-pillar.eu/>

² NI4OS-Europe. <https://ni4os.eu/>

³ EOSC-Nordic. <https://www.eosc-nordic.eu/>

⁴ EOSC Synergy. <https://www.eosc-synergy.eu/>

⁵ European Commission. (2015). *Validation of the results of the public consultation on Science 2.0: Science in Transition*. <https://ec.europa.eu/digital-single-market/en/news/final-report-science-20-public-consultation>

for analysing complex data from different sources” and to step up Open Science policies in Europe. Former EU Commission President Jean-Claude Juncker in his speech on 27th October 2015⁶ “*Construire l'Europe industrielle du numérique*” referred to “*une initiative pour créer un nuage européen pour la recherche consacrée à la science ouverte – a European Open Science Cloud.*” Preparation work was carried out by a High-Level Expert Group on European Open Science Cloud (HLEG) created in September 2015. The HLEG provided advice to the Commission on the strategy for the European Open Science Cloud initiative as part of the Digital Single Market.

In April 2016 the European Commission published the Communication “*European Cloud Initiative - Building a competitive data and knowledge economy in Europe*”⁷. The Communication formally established the strategy for the realization of the European Open Science Cloud as identified in the recommendation of the HLEG. The European Open Science Cloud was building on the achievements of the European Cloud Strategy⁸ and the High-Performance Computing (HPC) Strategy⁹. Following the recommendation of the HLEG, EOSC was seen as a federated environment for scientific data sharing and re-use, based on existing and emerging elements in the Member States, with lightweight international guidance and governance and a large degree of freedom regarding practical implementation¹⁰.

“The European Open Science Cloud aims to give Europe a global lead in scientific data infrastructures, to ensure that European scientists reap the full benefits of data-driven science. Practically, it will offer 1.7 million European researchers and 70 million professionals in science and technology a virtual environment with free at the point of use, open and seamless services for storage, management, analysis and re-use of research data, across borders and scientific disciplines. Its development will be driven by the scientific community, who are the most advanced users and the largest producers of science in the world. The European Open Science Cloud will be also open for education and training purposes in higher education and, over time, to government and business users as the technologies developed will be promoted for wider application”¹¹.

EOSC¹² is primarily a process to create an environment which makes research data in Europe accessible to all researchers under the same terms of use and distribution. It aims to establish a culture where open research data are findable, accessible, interoperable and re-usable (FAIR)¹³.

With the funding support of the H2020 research program, a first initiative was launched at the beginning of 2017: EOSC Pilot¹⁴ with an investment of 10 Million Euros to support the first phase of development of the

⁶ Speech of President of the European Commission Jean-Claude Juncker. (27 October 2015). *Construire l'Europe industrielle du numérique*. https://ec.europa.eu/commission/presscorner/detail/fr/SPEECH_15_5938

⁷ COM (2016) 178 final

⁸ COM (2012) 529 final

⁹ COM (2012) 45 final

¹⁰ European Commission. (2016). *Realising the European Open Science Cloud - First report and recommendations of the Commission High Level Expert Group on the European Open Science Cloud*. Luxembourg: Publications Office of the European Union. <https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/2ec2eced-9ac5-11e6-868c-01aa75ed71a1>

¹¹ COM (2016) 178 final

¹² Budroni, P., Claude-Burgelman, J., Schoupe, M., (2019). *Architectures of Knowledge: The European Open Science Cloud*. *ABI Technik*, 39 (2), 130-141. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1515/abitech-2019-2006>

¹³ FAIR data - Wikipedia. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/FAIR_data

¹⁴ EOSCpilot. <https://eoscpilot.eu/>

European Open Science Cloud as described in the EC Communication on European Cloud Initiatives of 2016. Timeline of the EOSC project implementation and related projects funding is represented in the image below (Figure 1).

Figure 1: EOSC Implementation Timeline

In the following years EOSC has emerged as a clear policy priority for EU investment. The Competitiveness Council held in Brussels on the 29 of May 2018, and the following adopted resolutions on EOSC¹⁵, considered the need for an open and trusted environment to manage research data, and confirmed the need to go ahead with EOSC implementation along the lines proposed in the EC staff working document Implementation Roadmap for the European Open Science Cloud¹⁶. These Council conclusions and the Implementation Roadmap built the foundation for subsequent EOSC development.

¹⁵ The European Open Data. <https://data.consilium.europa.eu/doc/document/ST-9029-2018-INIT/en/pdf>

¹⁶ Commission staff working document "Implementation Roadmap for the European Open Science Cloud", SWD (2018). <https://ec.europa.eu/transparency/regdoc/rep/10102/2018/EN/SWD-2018-83-F1-EN-MAIN-PART-1.PDF>

EC formally launched the EOSC at the University of Vienna¹⁷ in November 2018: the EOSC Portal¹⁸ was inaugurated. The implementation roadmap of 2018¹⁹ identified 5 fundamental requirements of the infrastructure:

- clear governance framework²⁰, a multi-level and multi-stakeholder governance^{21 22} with clear institutional, executive and advisory roles addressing the need for long-term public funding for the services²³;
- the definition of the initial services;
- a clear business model for research data repositories and networks that mixes sources of revenue for long-term sustainability²⁴;
- the facilitation of access and re-use;
- cost optimisation to be sought via synergies.

The EOSC is certainly not a novel infrastructure but the resulting of an ensemble of European wide infrastructures and of national ones. As mentioned earlier in this section, its aim is to make research data in Europe accessible to all researchers under the same terms of use and distribution encouraging a culture of open research data and FAIR²⁵ access.

At the moment of this report' data gathering (*e.g.*, August 2020), the EOSC Catalogue includes: 338 services; 4.4M datasets; 141k software and applications; 34.6M publications; and 3M other research products, offered by 138 service/resource providers and aggregators²⁶. The services are grouped in the following 8 categories: Compute, Data Management, Networking, Processing and Analysis, Security and Operations, Sharing and Discovery, Storage and Training and Support²⁷.

Among the most important initiatives for the Open Science movement, which can be considered the main building blocks of EOSC, we should consider:

EGI Federation²⁸: a federated e-infrastructure that provides advanced computing and data analytics for research and innovation. For more than a decade, it has been delivering large-scale data analysis capabilities to more than 70,000 researchers covering many scientific disciplines. Services include both technical and

¹⁷ EOSC Vienna Declaration. <https://eosc-launch.eu/declaration/>

¹⁸ EOSC Portal. <https://eosc-portal.eu/>

¹⁹ Commission staff working document "Implementation Roadmap for the European Open Science Cloud", SWD (2018) 83 final. <https://ec.europa.eu/transparency/regdoc/rep/10102/2018/EN/SWD-2018-83-F1-EN-MAIN-PART-1.PDF>

²⁰ EOSC Executive Board EOSC Portal. <https://www.eosc-portal.eu/governance/executive-board>

²¹ EOSC Governance Board EOSC Portal. <https://www.eosc-portal.eu/governance/eosc-board>

²² EOSC Stakeholders Forum EOSC Portal. <https://www.eosc-portal.eu/governance/stakeholders-forum>

²³ EU Research and Innovation programme for the 2014-2020 period, €600 million has been allocated to setting up EOSC: <https://ec.europa.eu/programmes/horizon2020/>

²⁴ EOSC Sustainability activity will provide a set of recommendations concerning the implementation of an operational, scalable and sustainable EOSC federation after 2020

²⁵ Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable

²⁶ EOSC Catalogue - EOSC Portal. <https://catalogue.eosc-portal.eu/>

²⁷ Browse service categories - EOSC Catalogue - EOSC Portal. <https://marketplace.eosc-portal.eu/>

²⁸ EGI.eu. <https://www.egi.eu/>

non-technical services, such as high-throughput and cloud computing, storage and data management services, consultancy and support, training and co-development. The EGI federation infrastructure comprises more than 200 data centres across Europe and worldwide offering access to more than 1 million CPUs and 1000 PB of disk and tape storage. The vision of EGI federation is to ensure that all researchers have seamless access to services, resources and expertise to collaborate and conduct world-class research and innovation. Today, the EGI Federation is funded through a combination of membership fees, national and EC funding and is governed by the EGI federation Foundation, which was established in 2010 as a not-for-profit legal entity under Dutch law in the Netherlands. The EGI federation Foundation has participants and associated participants drawn from NGIs, EIROs, ERICs, and other legal entities. These entities participate in the Foundation independently or as the representative of a national e-infrastructure consortium.

EUDAT²⁹ is a Collaborative Data Infrastructure (CDI), which manages data spanning from European research data centres and community data repositories. EUDAT aims to support sharing and preserving data across borders and disciplines. European researchers and practitioners from any research discipline can preserve, find, access, and process data in a trusted environment. EUDAT offers heterogeneous research data management services and storage resources, supporting multiple research communities as well as individuals, through a geographically distributed, resilient network distributed across 15 European countries. EUDAT offers common data services, supporting multiple research communities as well as individuals through a network of 36 European organisations. Its main services are the following: B2DROP³⁰, B2SHARE³¹, B2SAFE³², B2STAGE³³, B2FIND³⁴, B2HANDLE³⁵, B2ACCESS³⁶

GÉANT³⁷ is the basic e-infrastructure in Europe. GÉANT interconnects 38 National Research and Education Network (NREN) partners, and it is the largest and most advanced R&I network in the world. GÉANT connects over 50 million users at 10,000 institutions across Europe and supports all scientific disciplines. The backbone network operates at speeds of up to 500 Gbps and reaches over 100 national networks worldwide. Since its establishment over 20 years ago, the GÉANT network has progressively developed to ensure that European researchers lead international and global collaboration. GÉANT develops and delivers advanced networks and associated e-infrastructure services. It supports open innovation, collaboration and knowledge-sharing amongst its members, partners and the wider research and education networking community. With more than 40 partners and associates across Europe and a multi-million-euro budget, GÉANT network also offers

²⁹ EUDAT - Research Data Services, Expertise & Technology. <https://eudat.eu/>

³⁰ B2DROP - EUDAT. <https://www.eudat.eu/services/b2drop>

³¹ b2share - EUDAT. <https://b2share.eudat.eu/>

³² B2SAFE - EUDAT. <https://www.eudat.eu/b2safe>

³³ B2STAGE - EUDAT. <https://www.eudat.eu/b2stage>

³⁴ B2FIND - EUDAT. <https://eudat.eu/services/b2find>

³⁵ B2HANDLE - EUDAT. <https://www.eudat.eu/services/userdoc/b2handle>

³⁶ B2ACCESS - EUDAT. <https://eudat.eu/services/b2access>

³⁷ GÉANT. <https://www.geant.org/>

connectivity to other world regions (AfricaConnect2³⁸, CAREN³⁹, EUMED Connect3⁴⁰, EaPConnect⁴¹, TANDEM⁴² and others).

OpenAIRE⁴³ provides unlimited, open access to research outputs financed by public funding in Europe. OpenAIRE fulfils the EOSC vision substantially, as its operations already provide the “glue” for many of the users and research driven functionalities, whether these come from the long tail of science (repositories and local support) or domain disciplined research communities or research infrastructures. Scholarly communication initiatives and services are a relevant component of the current landscape, especially for the long tail of science. These initiatives originated from the movement to provide open access to scientific publications but are now applying open access principles to data (e.g., FAIR data) and other types of research products. OpenAIRE is a key initiative in this area which started as a supporting initiative for Open Access (OA) policy in FP7 and developing a set of mechanisms to implement and monitor Open Science in Europe in H2020. Services which OpenAIRE can provide within the EOSC are: a national network of 34 nodes (National Open Access Desks⁴⁴), which are expert organisations offering local support, training and policy alignment on open access and research Data Management (RDM). The OpenAIRE Guidelines for Content providers⁴⁵ and related services to allow content providers to make publications, data, software available in EOSC following FAIR principles. A set of services to help researchers do Open Science: Zenodo⁴⁶ – a catch-all repository, Argos⁴⁷ – an actionable DMP service linked to EU and national infrastructures, Amnesia⁴⁸ – an anonymisation tool, the OpenAIRE Research Graph⁴⁹, a global contextual catalogue of research results linked together which is the basis for intelligent, AI-based discovery and the Open Science Observatory⁵⁰ to monitor different aspects of Open Science in Europe. OpenAIRE-Advance⁵¹ continues the mission of OpenAIRE to support the Open Access/Open Data mandates in Europe, in particular it has the aim to empower its National Open Access Desks (NOADs) so they can become a pivotal part within their own national data infrastructures, positioning OA and Open Science onto national agendas. To ensure persistent existence of OpenAIRE support and services beyond projects, OpenAIRE established a legal entity called OpenAIRE AMKE to provide structure for a European-wide national policy and open scholarly communication infrastructure. OpenAIRE AMKE with currently 36 regular and 3 associated members⁵², offers European-wide coverage of the OpenAIRE-Advance project.

³⁸ AfricaConnect2. <https://www.africaconnect2.net/Pages/Welcome%20to%20AfricaConnect2.html>

³⁹ CAREN. <https://caren.geant.org/Pages/Welcome%20to%20the%20CAREN%20website.html>

⁴⁰ EUMEDCONNECT3. <https://www.eumedconnect3.net/Pages/Home.aspx>

⁴¹ EaP Connect. <https://www.eapconnect.eu/>

⁴² TANDEM WACREN. <https://www.tandem-wacren.eu/about-tandem/project-key-facts/>

⁴³ OpenAIRE. <https://www.openaire.eu/>

⁴⁴ OpenAIRE Noad Activities. <https://www.openaire.eu/noad-activities>

⁴⁵ OpenAIRE Guidelines. <https://guidelines.openaire.eu/>

⁴⁶ Zenodo. <https://zenodo.org/>

⁴⁷ Argos - OpenAIRE. <https://argos.openaire.eu/>

⁴⁸ Amnesia - OpenAIRE. <https://amnesia.openaire.eu/>

⁴⁹ OpenAIRE Research Graph. <https://www.openaire.eu/blogs/the-openaire-research-graph>

⁵⁰ Service at <https://beta.observatory.openaire.eu>

⁵¹ OpenAIRE Mission and Vision. <https://www.openaire.eu/mission-and-vision>

⁵² AMKE Members. <https://www.openaire.eu/amke-members>

PRACE⁵³ is a pan-European supercomputing infrastructure for large-scale scientific and engineering applications at the highest performance level. Four hosting members (BS⁵⁴ in Spain, CINECA⁵⁵ in Italy, GCS⁵⁶ in Germany and GENCI⁵⁷ in France) secured funding for the initial period from 2010 to 2016. In 2017, PRACE launched the second period of the Partnership, securing the operations of the infrastructure until 2020, adding a fifth Hosting Member: ETHZ⁵⁸ in Switzerland. During this second phase, PRACE will offer an initial performance above 62 Petaflops in 7 complementary leading-edge systems, offering a total of 4000 million core hours per year (75 million node hours).

RDA Europe 4.0⁵⁹ The Research Data Alliance is an international community driven initiative building social and technical bridges to enable the open sharing and re-use of research data. The RDA Europe 4.0 project is mandated to ensure that European political, research, industrial and digital infrastructure stakeholders are aware and actively involved in the global RDA activities. RDA provides an international neutral forum for discussing and agreeing relevant technical standards for the implementation of the EOSC. In addition, RDA supports the communication and dissemination of EOSC developments across the globe.

EURO HPC⁶⁰ is a joint undertaking initiative between the EU, European countries and private partners to develop a World Class Supercomputing Ecosystem in Europe. The main aim of EURO HPC is to enhance European network in high performance computing (HPC), providing computing solutions, improving cooperation in advanced scientific research, boosting industrial competitiveness, and ensuring European technological and digital autonomy.

Amongst the other initiatives to be considered under the umbrella of European Open Science activities, it is worth mentioning FAIRsFAIR which has been a project funded after the establishment of EOSC in order to support it.

FAIRsFAIR⁶¹ aims to supply practical solutions for the use of the FAIR data principles throughout the research data life cycle with an emphasis on advancing FAIR data culture and the uptake of good practices in making data FAIR, in particular in the context of the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC). FAIRsFAIR delivers and supports recommendations on data policy and practice, provides solutions and support for semantic interoperability, support certification of trustworthy data repositories and data assessment, as well as develop a FAIR competence centre and framework for higher education.

⁵³ PRACE. <https://prace-ri.eu/>

⁵⁴ BSC Barcelona Supercomputing Center. <https://www.bsc.es/>

⁵⁵ Cineca. <http://www.cineca.it/>

⁵⁶ Gauss Centre for Supercomputing. <https://www.gauss-centre.eu/>

⁵⁷ Genci. <http://www.genci.fr/>

⁵⁸ ETH Zürich. <https://ethz.ch/de.html>

⁵⁹ RDA EU 4.0 RDA Europe. <https://www.rd-alliance.org/rda-europe>

⁶⁰ EuroHPC Joint Undertaking. <https://eurohpc-ju.europa.eu/>

⁶¹ FAIRsFAIR. <https://www.fairsfair.eu/the-project>

Other Open Science initiatives outside Europe

Outside Europe, the Open Science movement is clearly driven by US initiatives: Open Science Framework⁶², The Mendeley Data⁶³ (with 24.9 million datasets from domain-specific and cross-domain repositories), National Data Service⁶⁴, Dryad digital repository⁶⁵ and Harvard Dataverse⁶⁶, ScienceOpen⁶⁷ (which collects 64 million publications and 25 thousand journals), Unpaywall⁶⁸, CyVerse⁶⁹, and Google Dataset Search are the main ones⁷⁰. Other relevant initiatives are the Canada Federated Research Data Repository⁷¹, the Australian National Data Service⁷² hosting the Research Data Australia discovery portal⁷³, and the NCI National Research Data Collection⁷⁴. Additionally, there are relevant Open e-Science infrastructures that support the storage and analysis research data, such as the Open Science Grid⁷⁵ in USA and Compute in Canada⁷⁶.

In 2016, The Amsterdam Call to Action⁷⁷ outlined the actions Member States and different actors in the research system would have to make to implement Open Science. In spite of the efforts and investments done the complexity of the project present some relevant challenges. These are various and mainly depend on different policy alignment across local, regional, national and international jurisdictions and the need to harmonise legal and regulatory frameworks.

For example, involvement of private sector in EOSC activities has been promoted through the EOSC Digital Innovation Hub⁷⁸ (DIH). This initiative aims to develop mechanisms for private companies to collaborate with public sector institutions within the European Open Science Cloud in order to access technical services, research data, and human capital. The interesting pilots developed in that context are a promising start, but a wider interest and engagement of the private sector community and business models and engagement strategy needs to be clarified to increase participation. Clearly this is also linked to the development of human capacity within the Open Science movement: for this Open Science education and training, tailored to the research careers, should explore the needs between academia and industry concerning the Open Science challenges in public-private partnerships in particular regarding IPR management. Moreover, emerging technological areas should be taken in consideration in the EOSC strategic development also to keep up with industrial interests and infrastructure uptake. Technology developments like blockchain, artificial

⁶² OSF.io. <https://osf.io/>

⁶³ Mendeley Data. <https://data.mendeley.com/>

⁶⁴ National Data Service. <http://www.nationaldataservice.org/>

⁶⁵ Data Dryad. <https://datadryad.org/stash>

⁶⁶ Harvard Dataverse. <https://dataverse.harvard.edu/>

⁶⁷ ScienceOpen. <https://www.scienceopen.com/>

⁶⁸ Unpaywall. <https://unpaywall.org/>

⁶⁹ The Project CyVerse. <https://cyverse.org/about>

⁷⁰ Dataset Search Google. <https://toolbox.google.com/datasetsearch/search?query=10.5064>

⁷¹ Data Publication FRDR-DFDR. <https://www.frdr-dfdr.ca/repo/>

⁷² Home ANDS. <https://www.ands.org.au/>

⁷³ Research Data Australia ANDS. <https://www.ands.org.au/online-services/research-data-australia>

⁷⁴ Data Collections Management NCI. <https://nci.org.au/our-services/data-collections-management>

⁷⁵ Open Science Grid. <https://opensciencegrid.org/>

⁷⁶ Compute Canada. <https://www.computecanada.ca/home/>

⁷⁷ *Amsterdam Call to Action on Open Science*. (2016).

<https://www.government.nl/documents/reports/2016/04/04/amsterdam-call-for-action-on-open-science>

⁷⁸ EOSC DIH. <https://eosc-dih.eu/>

intelligence, cybersecurity, edge and fog computing are topics of relevance in the Open Science discourse and could play a role in the discussion on the EOOSC development strategy.

Another emerging topic, following the new Commission strategy on greening the EU economy, is the alignment of EOOSC to the new European Green Deal initiatives, promoting a Green-EOOSC approach.

The Final Report of the Open Science Policy Platform⁷⁹ Working group published in April 2020 identifies more barriers to be removed to implement a Shared Research Knowledge System by 2030 with a call for action based on five shared attributes of the next to come research cycle (see Table 1 below).

<p>Attribute 1: An academic career structure that rewards a broad range of outputs, practices and behaviours to maximise contributions to a shared research knowledge system</p>	<p>A key barrier to the diffusion and exchange of scholarly knowledge is the current reward system. There is no researcher, no institution and no discipline that is not negatively affected by a system based on rewarding a very limited set of research behaviours, outputs and venues. Publicly and privately funded research, intellectual property rights (IPRs) must be embedded within an Open Science framework that protects the interests of different stakeholders, including private and commercial research organisations but without limiting the scientific and societal benefits of sharing and reuse of scholarly knowledge for all humanity</p>
<p>Attribute 2: A research system that is reliable, transparent and trustworthy</p>	<p>Utility of a shared research knowledge system depends on ensuring that there is trust in the research process and the reliability of the outputs, and in the ways data and results are made reusable and re-used. Lack of awareness, support, training and leadership around research and publication ethics and integrity, in particular among researchers⁸⁰</p>
<p>Attribute 3: A research system that enables innovation</p>	<p>A shared research system for innovation must include Clear relevant policies that aim to increase the availability and reuse of research knowledge and technology in a global competitive context Global interoperable infrastructure of tools, services, hardware and software Clear regulatory frameworks to manage each stakeholder's interests for the collective good A transparent competitive market A shared research system based on reciprocity</p>
<p>Attribute 4: A research culture that facilitates diversity and equity of opportunity</p>	<p>All actors need to work together to articulate the shared values for a shared global research knowledge system and to create a legal and social framework within which these values can be implemented.</p>
<p>Attribute 5: A research system that is built on evidence-based policy and practice</p>	<p>Understand how, where and when new ways of working and changes to existing, and perhaps entrenched practices and work should be changed. More activity needed around meta-research</p>

⁷⁹ *Progress on Open Science: Towards a Shared Research Knowledge System – Final Report of the Open Science Policy Platform.* (2020). Luxembourg: Publications Office of the European Union. <https://doi.org/10.2777/00139>

⁸⁰ *What Researchers Think about the Culture They Work in 'Welcome'.* (2020). <https://wellcome.ac.uk/reports/what-researchers-think-about-research-culture>

	(or ‘science of science’). It’s recommended that a coordinated strategy for funding and delivering a programme of ‘research on research’ is developed, including identifying priority areas for investigation, involving representatives from the key stakeholders in research – researchers, funding agencies, institutions, publishers, learned societies and others.
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Table 1: Barriers to implement a Shared Research Knowledge System by 2030⁸¹

1.2 Complementarities with other reports and policy documents

Since 2015 there’s been a relevant production of reports and policy documents framing the actions and the regulatory framework for the implementation and adoption of the European Science Cloud. In this context the European Open Science Policy Platform played a relevant role in facilitating the exchange between universities, research organizations, academies and learned societies, funding organizations, citizen science organizations, publishers, Open Science platforms and intermediaries and Libraries⁸².

The Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda (SRIA) of the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC)⁸³ identifies landscape monitoring as one of the boundary conditions of the EOSC ecosystem deployment in particular requiring that information gathered in the analysis must be kept up to date supported by a set of relevant key performance indicators (KPIs).

The Landscape Working Group (WG) of the EOSC Executive Board mapped the existing research infrastructures in Europe and the regulations and policies to be considered in its design and development. The result of this work is included in the “**Landscape of EOSC-related infrastructures and initiatives**” report published on November 2020⁸⁴. It provides information on existing policies and investments based on inputs from the member states and on the expert knowledge of the Working Group members and delegates to the EOSC Governance Board. The work of the landscaping WG is complementary with the one carried out in this report. Indeed, while the information here reported represents the vision of several actors mainly, but not solely, within the OS community, the Landscaping WG analysis offers a higher level and institutional vision on the same or related topics covered by this analysis.

This report complements the long-term monitoring of EOSC landscape. The contribution of this study should inform the boundary conditions to “Ensure continuous monitoring of the existing readiness of countries to

⁸¹ European Commission. (2020). *Progress on Open Science: Towards a Shared Research Knowledge System – Final Report of the Open Science Policy Platform*. Luxembourg: Publications Office of the European Union. 2020. <https://doi.org/10.2777/00139>

⁸² European Open Science Policy Platform.

<https://ec.europa.eu/transparency/regexpert/index.cfm?do=groupDetail.groupDetail&groupID=3436&NewSearch=1&NewSearch=1>

⁸³ *Open Consultation for the Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda (SRIA) of the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC)*. (2020). https://www.eoscsecretariat.eu/sites/default/files/open_consultation_booklet_sria-eosc_20-july-2020.pdf

⁸⁴ European Commission. (2020). *Landscape of EOSC-related infrastructures and initiatives*. DOI: 10.2777/132181. <https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/9c7f3c1e-2aea-11eb-9d7e-01aa75ed71a1/language-en/format-PDF/source-173604556>

contribute to EOSC (p. 13)” and to “Suggest priorities for action based on the monitoring” (p. 14)⁸⁵ as described in the Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda (SRIA) document.

2 A collaborative effort: the methodological approach of the report

As mentioned in the introduction, the aim of this report is to provide an overview of the point of view towards EOSC and of related practises of EOSC-relevant stakeholders in 35 countries, mapping their familiarity with EOSC and Open Science (OS) and gathering information on the services they provide, their user communities and on the policies in place.

This is a *secondary analysis* based on the results of studies conducted by four EU-funded regional projects: EOSC-Pillar, NI4OS-Europe, EOSC-Nordic and EOSC-Synergy, whose common goal is supporting the participation and coordination of national actors to EOSC. Each project focuses on specific countries and has, then, additional specific objectives which are mentioned here after⁸⁶.

EOSC-Pillar⁸⁷ focuses on **Austria, Belgium, France, Germany and Italy**. It integrates a bottom-up approach (by voicing the requirements and needs expressed by the different scientific communities) and a top-down one (by harmonising the national strategies and translating them in a viable work plan). In the longer term, this is expected to facilitate the design and adoption of common policies and streamline the process of joining EOSC for service providers and user communities while helping to populate EOSC with useful services of wider European interest.

NI4OS-Europe⁸⁸ supports the development and inclusion of the national Open Science Cloud initiatives in 15 Member States and Associated Countries in the EOSC governance. The countries covered are **Romania, Bulgaria, Hungary, Greece, Slovenia, Serbia, Bosnia-Herzegovina, Albania, Montenegro, North Macedonia, Moldova, Croatia, Georgia, Cyprus and Armenia**. Moreover, the project aims to promote the EOSC philosophy and FAIR principles within the community and provides technical and policy support for on-boarding of service providers into EOSC.

EOSC-Nordic⁸⁹ focuses on the Nordic and Baltic countries (**Finland, Sweden, Iceland, Denmark, Norway, Latvia, Lithuania and Estonia**) and aims to exploit synergies to achieve greater harmonisation at policy and service provisioning level across these countries, in compliance with EOSC agreed standards and practices. In addition, the project facilitates the coordination of EOSC-relevant initiatives focusing on policies, service provisioning and research data, in light of the EOSC requirements.

EOSC-Synergy⁹⁰ aims at expanding the capacity and capabilities of EOSC by leveraging the experience, effort and resources of national publicly funded digital infrastructures. It pursues this goal by working on capacity building, capability development, the promotion of software quality, policy harmonisation and human capital

⁸⁵ *Open Consultation for the Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda (SRIA) of the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC)*. (2020). https://www.eoscsecretariat.eu/sites/default/files/open_consultation_booklet_sria-eosc_20-july-2020.pdf

⁸⁶ The information reported are quoted by the projects’ public websites or elaboration of their contents.

⁸⁷ EOSC-Pillar. <https://www.eosc-pillar.eu/>

⁸⁸ NI4OS-Europe. <https://ni4os.eu/>

⁸⁹ EOSC-Nordic. <https://www.eosc-nordic.eu/>

⁹⁰ EOSC Synergy. <https://www.eosc-synergy.eu/>

development. The project focuses on the following countries: **Czech Republic, Portugal, United Kingdom, Spain, The Netherlands, Poland and Slovakia.**

The backbone of this study is “EOSC-Pillar National Initiatives Survey”⁹¹ developed by the EOSC-Pillar project and adopted, at least to a certain extent, by other territorial projects. The questionnaire targets four different stakeholders which are: e-infrastructures⁹², research infrastructures of national relevance, universities and funding bodies. All the stakeholders received a common set of questions, plus others tailored to their specific profile.

EOSC-Nordic adopted this questionnaire without substantial changes while the other projects adjusted it to the specificities of their project’s needs. More precisely:

NI4OS-Europe changed the wording of some questions in order to better reflect the needs of their stakeholders, removed 12 questions and added new questions related to complementary research activities of the project. Furthermore, considering the EOSC-Pillar questionnaire, which contained a set of questions seeking to assess respondents’ awareness of, readiness for and expectations from EOSC, the reference to EOSC in the NI4OS-Europe questions is more implicit rather than explicit.

EOSC-Synergy used a shortened version⁹³ of the “EOSC-Pillar National Initiatives Survey” in two countries (Czech Republic and Portugal) and, for the other countries, it provided information on the main topics covered by it through desk study, analysis of existing surveys and reports and dedicated interviews. The project produced individual country reports⁹⁴ which present mainly qualitative information although they include secondary data analysis of pre-existing statistical information too.

Overall, this report considered 33 survey questions that were in common among two or more projects, while excluded those questions that were asked only by one project. Small differences in the wording of few questions, or in the definition of the involved stakeholders, persist and are described in more detail in the data analysis paragraph (paragraph 2.3).

The definition of stakeholders was somehow different in some of the projects. Indeed, EOSC-Nordic considered six stakeholder groups: the four considered in the “EOSC-Pillar National Initiatives Survey” (e-infrastructures⁹⁵, research infrastructures of national relevance, universities and funding bodies), plus the category “other” and for the survey in Finland the category “research institutes/similar” was also added. NI4OS-Europe, in order to better reflect the situation in the countries under analysis, many of which are less

⁹¹ Bodlos, Anita; Hönegger, Lisa; Kaczmirek, Lars; Beckmann, Volker; Breton, Vincent; Romier, Geneviève; Van Wezel, Jos; Streit, Achim; Stevanovic, Uros; Galeazzi, Fulvio; Tanlongo, Federica; Van Nieuwerburgh, Inge. (2019). “EOSC Pillar “National Initiatives” Survey (SUF edition)”, AUSSDA, V1. <https://doi.org/10.11587/VOSVGK>

⁹² In the definition of the target groups data repositories, data archives, data/computing centres, grid infrastructure, HPC’s, NREN’s and national museums with digital archives are included under the category e-infrastructures

⁹³ Seven questions of the EOSC-Pillar questionnaire were not included in the EOSC-Synergy ‘one.

⁹⁴ All reports are available at the project website, in the home page: <https://www.eosc-synergy.eu/> by clicking on each country code in the map at the bottom of the page. CZ: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3891370>; ES: <https://doi.org/10.20350/digitalCSIC/12624>; NL: <https://doi.org/10.17026/dans-2by-ereu>; PL: <https://doi.org/10.20350/digitalCSIC/12625>; PT: https://doi.org/10.34642/fccn_bep7-qk29; SK: <https://doi.org/10.20350/digitalCSIC/12626>; UK: <https://doi.org/10.20350/digitalCSIC/12631>

⁹⁵ In the definition of the target groups data repositories, data archives, data/computing centres, grid infrastructure, HPC’s, NREN’s and national museums with digital archives are included under the category e-infrastructures

structured in terms of Open Science compared to most of the EU countries, followed a slightly different approach. Indeed, NI4OS-Europe took as starting point the main functions of Open Science and considered five relevant stakeholder groups labelled Fund, Create, Support, Consume and Open Science facilitators. They include and largely reflect the stakeholder groups considered by EOSC Pillar and EOSC-Nordic, but include also SMEs and citizens, which are potential users of Open Science services and Open Science facilitators and ambassadors, that are particularly relevant in the landscape of some of the countries represented in the project. Here below a more detailed description of the NI4OS-Europe stakeholder groups:

- **FUND** - Funders and policymakers
- **CREATE** - The ones who perform research, including research performing organizations, researchers, research communities, citizen scientists and data and Open Science enthusiasts.
- **SUPPORT** - The ones who perform research as repositories, research infrastructures, e-infrastructures, service providers and libraries (esp. academic and research libraries).
- **CONSUME** - The ones who “consume” research as SMEs, and other companies which could benefit from the use of open technologies and open data in creating new products and new technologies and citizens.
- **FACILITATE** - Open Science facilitators (including Open Science initiatives), including international nodes and beneficiaries representing European or national initiatives for Open Science⁹⁶.

Finally, with reference to EOSC-Synergy, in the two countries in which the survey was conducted, the stakeholders targeted were as follows:

- in Portugal: research infrastructures and e-infrastructures;
- in Czech Republic, research infrastructures, e-infrastructures and Founders.

Table 2 summarises the stakeholders addressed by each project.

Stakeholders/ Projects	Research Infrastructures	E-Infrastructures	Universities	Funding Bodies	Other
EOSC-Pillar	●	●	●	●	
NI4OS-Europe	●	●		●	Researchers, Citizen scientists, SMEs, Academic and research libraries, Repositories, Open Science facilitators
EOSC-Nordic	●	●	●	●	For Finland only: research institute/similar
EOSC-Synergy	●	●		●	

⁹⁶Biljana Kosanović, & Milica Ševkušić. (2019, December 30). *NI4OS-Europe Stakeholder map, inventory, policy matrix*. Zenodo. <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3736129>

Table 2: Stakeholders by project

Overall, of the 35 countries considered in this landscaping analysis, 30 were involved in a questionnaire-based survey whereas five were not (United Kingdom, Spain, Slovakia, Poland and The Netherlands). The information provided for these five countries are included in the statistical analysis when possible, otherwise they are reported as additional, qualitative, information.

2.1 Research questions

The nature of this research is *exploratory and descriptive*: it provides information useful to the EOSC governance and the EC to better design and implement the future actions for the fulfilment of EOSC agenda. It aims to collect the point of view of Open Science stakeholders providing answers to the following questions:

- How knowledgeable are Open Science actors with reference to EOSC and the FAIR principles?
- What are the perceived benefits of EOSC and the respondents' organisation potentialities in terms of contribution to EOSC?
- What are the Open Science services already available in the various countries, who are the main users and how are the services provided and regulated?
- What is the status of Open Science in terms of policies and roadmaps?
- How is Open Science funded currently and what are the sustainability models in place?

2.2 Data gathering process

As mentioned in the previous sub-section, this report builds on the data gathered by EOSC-Pillar, NI4OS-Europe, EOSC-Nordic and EOSC-Synergy. The authors worked together with representatives of those projects in the period between November 2019 and July 2020 facilitating the alignment – as much as possible – of the four-research design and data gathering processes.

The four projects collected and elaborated the data in different moments between September 2019 and June 2020. Then, the data was transferred to the authors, in some cases the authors got access to the overall curated dataset, in other cases the project provided the frequency tables for the topics considered here while, in other cases, the information was included in more qualitative, analytical reports and the relevant data was extracted by the authors.

Considering the above-mentioned process, it is worth describing the data gathering process followed by the four territorial projects:

EOSC-Pillar data gathering process started by compiling a comprehensive list of organisations and individuals. Contact details for the different countries under analysis and for the different stakeholders' categories were considered. The list was developed by using public databases and listings including those of national and international Open Science related organisations. For each organisation, a contact person was identified, usually a scientific or managing director of the given organisation. Those experts "*received an invitation to participate in the survey as representatives of their organisation and were asked to provide answers and to gather relevant information within the organisation if necessary*" (Bodlos et al.2019).

EOSC-Nordic and NI4OS-Europe relied more on the partners' knowledge so that each country representative within the consortium created a list of contacts to be invited and then followed a similar process of the one carried out by EOSC-Pillar. EOSC-Pillar, EOSC-Nordic and NI4OS-Europe gathered data through an online questionnaire powered by LimeSurvey⁹⁷. The majority of questions were mandatory, and the questionnaires were anonymous.

Also, in the case of EOSC-Synergy the role of the consortium partners was crucial, as mentioned earlier, an online survey was carried out in the period between February 2020 and May 2020 for Portugal and Czech Republic; while for the other countries a more qualitative, desk research-based approach was followed leading to a country report each.

2.3 Description of the sample and data analysis

It is important to underline that the sample of this analysis **is not statistically representative** because, out of the four projects whose data have been used for developing this report, only one of them (EOSC-Pillar) used a statistically representative sample while the other used a convenience sample. All the analysis presented in this report should be, therefore, seen as *exploratory and preliminary*, especially those carried out at country level for which the sizes of the samples show important differences (see Table 3). Moreover, in the OESC-Nordic's survey, some questions show a response rate lower than others so that additional attention is needed in using data at country level. Therefore, this report provides a preliminary map of the Open Science landscape, but further research will be needed in order to provide more solid evidence, especially at country level.

Overall, the secondary data analysis elaborated in this report refer to 1322 observations and covers 30 countries. Not all the questions were addressed to all the respondents and not all the questionnaires were complete: the exact number of collected answers for each question is reported in the analysis.

Table 3 reports the number of respondents (observations). per country and the percentage value on the total sample. Italy, with 219 observations, Germany with 186 and France with 102 observations are the countries with the highest number of collected answers, while Iceland (7), Norway (5 observations) and Lithuania (3) are countries with fewer respondents.

⁹⁷ LimerSurvey. <https://www.limesurvey.org/>

Countries	Ab. Val.	%
Albania	11	0.8%
Armenia	11	0.8%
Austria	48	3.6%
Belgium	48	3.6%
Bosnia – Herzegovina	20	1.5%
Bulgaria	43	3.2%
Croatia	76	5.7%
Cyprus	34	2.5%
Czech Republic	23	1.7%
Denmark	14	1%
Estonia	9	0.6%
Finland	13	0.9%
France	102	7.7%
Georgia	20	1.5%
Germany	186	14%
Greece	30	2.2%
Hungary	31	2.3%
Iceland	7	0.5%
Italy	219	16.5%
Latvia	11	0.8%
Lithuania	3	0.2%
Moldova	95	7.1%
Montenegro	19	1.4%
North Macedonia	37	2.8%
Norway	5	0.3%
Portugal	37	2.8%
Romania	51	3.8%
Serbia	56	4.2%
Slovenia	41	3.1%
Sweden	22	1.6%
Total	1322	100%

Table 3: Number of observations per country

The difference in size of the gathered observations is visualised in the figure that follows.

Figure 2: Geographical distribution of respondents at European level

It is worth considering that the population of the Nordic countries is smaller than those in the other countries here considered and, more generally there are relevant difference among the population of the various countries⁹⁸. Furthermore, the number of institutions working in the R&I field also differs considerable⁹⁹: Table 4 reports on these differences that have to be considered while reading the following analysis.

At the same time, it would be misleading to say that the information on, for example, Iceland is not representative considering the low number of respondents. Indeed, Iceland being a small country, few experts responding to the questionnaire are be more than sufficient to depict the country's awareness in terms of Open Science. Nevertheless, there is no way of clarifying this aspect as the questionnaires are anonymous by design. Therefore, *the reader should keep constantly in consideration the limitation of this sample when reading the following analysis and recall the exploratory nature of this research.*

⁹⁸ Resident Population by country on 1st January 2019 for the following countries (Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Croatia, Cyprus, Czech Republic, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, France, Germany, Hungary, Italy, Latvia, Lithuania) https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/demo_urespop/default/table?lang=en. Population on 1 January by age and sex (2019) for the following countries: Albania, Armenia, Georgia, North-Macedonia, Montenegro, Serbia, Moldova, Norway, Iceland. https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/demo_pjan/default/table?lang=en

⁹⁹ "Total Number of Researchers employed by sectors of performance (total number referred to Business and Enterprise Sector, Government Sector, Higher Education Sector, Private Non-Profit Sector): Full time equivalent" - Researchers are professionals engaged in the conception or creation of new knowledge, products, processes, methods and systems, and in the management of the projects concerned. FTE (Full-time equivalent) corresponds to one year's work by one person (for example, a person who devotes 40 % of his time to R&D is counted as 0.4 FTE, for the following countries: Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Croatia, Cyprus, Czech Republic, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, France, Germany, Greece, Hungary, Iceland, Italy, Latvia, Lithuania, Norway, Portugal, Romania, Serbia, Slovenia, Sweden. EUROSTAT. (2018). <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tsc00004/default/table?lang=en>

Countries	Observations by country (ab. val.)	Population by country	Number of Researchers employed by country
Albania	11	2.862.427	N/A ¹⁰⁰
Armenia	11	2.956.269	3.4 ¹⁰¹
Austria	48	8.842.000	50.484
Belgium	48	11.467.923	57.898
Bosnia – Herzegovina ¹⁰²	20	3.531.159	N/A
Bulgaria	43	7.000.039	16.521
Croatia	76	4.076.246	7.895
Cyprus	34	875.898	1.217
Czech Republic	23	10.528.984	41.198
Denmark	14	5.799.763	46.396
Estonia	9	1.324.820	4.968
Finland	13	5.512.119	37.891
France	102	67.028.048	306.451
Georgia	20	3.723.464	N/A
Germany	186	82.940.663	433.685
Greece	30	10.722.287	36.688
Hungary	31	9.772.756	37.606
Iceland	7	356.991	2.050
Italy	219	61.068.437	152.307
Latvia	11	1.919.968	3.456
Lithuania	3	2.794.184	8.938
Moldova	95	3.550.852	2.5 ¹⁰³
Montenegro	19	622.182	0.2073 ¹⁰⁴
North Macedonia	37	2.077.132	0.2226 ¹⁰⁵
Norway	5	5.328.212	34.337
Portugal	37	10.276.617	47.652
Romania	51	19.405.156	17.213

¹⁰⁰ Data not available in a comparable form with other sources

¹⁰¹ Ratio of number of researchers per 1000 Inhabitants-based on full-time equivalent units):

[https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php?title=File:Research %26 development personnel and researchers, 2013-2018 \(thousands of full-time equivalents\) ENPE20.png](https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php?title=File:Research_%26_development_personnel_and_researchers,_2013-2018_(thousands_of_full-time_equivalents)_ENPE20.png)

¹⁰² Latest updated official Census - Bosnia Herzegovina (2013), Bosnia-Herzegovina “Agency for Statistics of Bosnia Herzegovina”: <http://www.bhas.ba>

¹⁰³ Ratio of number of researchers per 1000 Inhabitants-based on full-time equivalent units):

[https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php?title=File:Research %26 development personnel and researchers, 2013-2018 \(thousands of full-time equivalents\) ENPE20.png](https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php?title=File:Research_%26_development_personnel_and_researchers,_2013-2018_(thousands_of_full-time_equivalents)_ENPE20.png)

¹⁰⁴ [https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php/R %26 D personnel#Researchers](https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php/R_%26_D_personnel#Researchers). (2018). “Total Number of Researchers employed by sectors of performance (total number referred to Business and Enterprise Sector, Government Sector, Higher Education Sector, Private Non-Profit Sector), Full time equivalent “Researchers are professionals engaged in the conception or creation of new knowledge, products, processes, methods and systems, and in the management of the projects concerned. FTE (Full-time equivalent) corresponds to one year’s work by one person (for example, a person who devotes 40 % of his time to R&D is counted as 0.4 FTE

¹⁰⁵ https://appsso.eurostat.ec.europa.eu/nui/show.do?dataset=rd_p_perscitz&lang=en. (2018). “Total Number of Researchers employed by sectors of performance (total number referred to Business and Enterprise Sector, Government Sector, Higher Education Sector, Private Non-Profit Sector): Full time equivalent”.

Serbia	56	6.963.764	14.535
Slovenia	41	2.080.908	10.068
Sweden	22	10.243.000	75.151
Total		1322	100%

Table 4: Population and number of researchers employed by country

The difference in sample size among the four regional projects also concurs in explaining the just-mentioned difference in country coverages. The table below (Table 5) shows how many completed questionnaires were gathered by each of the four regional projects.

EOOSC-Pillar	NI4OS-Europe	EOOSC-Nordic	EOOSC-Synergy	Total
603¹⁰⁶	575	84	60	1322

Table 5: Number of respondents per project

As mentioned, the authors aggregated the data coming from the survey carried out by four projects carrying on a secondary data analysis including all the responses gathered and associated with a country. In the case of EOOSC-Nordic, there were 22 records not associated with a country which has been excluded in order to be able to better carry out an analysis at country level and also because those entries were largely incomplete¹⁰⁷.

For each topic under analysis this report offers an overview at aggregated level (30 countries coverage), then - data allowing - an analysis at country level is provided. After the analysis of the data derived by the survey, the authors summarize the information provided by EOOSC-Synergy through desk research and secondary data analysis for those countries (5) in which the survey was not administered.

Considering that the four projects defined their stakeholders and respondents in a non-homogeneous way, an analysis by stakeholder category was not possible without compromising the logic of the original surveys. However, for those topics that refer to specific categories of stakeholders, the category of belonging of respondents is reported on a project-by-project base.

3 Stakeholder knowledge and vision on EOOSC

This chapter investigates the vision of interviewed actors towards EOOSC, more precisely:

- their familiarity with EOOSC and with the FAIR principles;
- the perceived benefits of joining EOOSC;
- their possible contribution to EOOSC;

¹⁰⁶ In the case of EOOSC-Pillar, also partial responses (85 collected answers) have been taken into account in some specific questions (*i.e.*, familiarity with EOOSC); considering that, the total number of observations in those questions is 688.

¹⁰⁷ It is worth mentioning that it was possible to take into consideration these 22 records for only two questions addressing the familiarity with EOOSC and the FAIR principles; hence they have been considered to have a bigger picture for the EOOSC-Nordic scenario, but they have been not included in the overall analysis because they were largely incomplete on the other responses.

- their collaboration with Open Science networks.

3.1 Familiarity with EOSC and FAIR principles

To provide an overview of the possible engagement with EOSC, it has been asked to the respondents how familiar they were with EOSC. Out of 1349 respondents (657 from EOSC-Pillar, 571 from NI4OS-Europe, 84 from EOSC-Nordic and 37 from the EOSC-Synergy report on Portugal), 11.2% (*ab. val.* 151) of them stated to be “very familiar” with EOSC, 40.3% (*ab. val.* 544) to be “familiar” with EOSC, 33.2% (*ab. val.* 448) to be “not very familiar” and 15.3% (*ab. val.* 206) to be “not familiar at all”.

Figure 3: Familiarity with EOSC

On average 51.5% of the respondents are familiar or very familiar with EOSC; not surprisingly the percentage of respondents that are familiar with EOSC differs from country to country¹⁰⁸.

The analysis at countries level was carried out only for those countries with a minimum of 50 collected answers, which are: Austria, Belgium, France, Germany, Italy, Serbia, Croatia, Romania.

¹⁰⁸ As we mentioned above, in the case of EOSC-Nordic, out of 84 total collected observations referred to a specific country, other 22 collected answers were recorded even though not specifically referred to any country. For this question, out of 2 “empty” total records, it was possible to take into consideration 20 records more to be added to the final EOSC-Nordic analysis: 8 records more for “familiar” (92 total records); 6 records for “not very familiar” (90 total records); 4 records more for “not familiar at all” and 2 records more for “very familiar” (86 total records).

Figure 4 shows that while in Italy, Serbia, Croatia and Romania the number of respondents familiar with EOSC is higher than the number of those who are not, the opposite is true in Austria, Germany and France. In Belgium the respondents are almost evenly split in the two groups.

Figure 4: Familiarity with EOSC by country

The survey also investigated the respondents' familiarity with FAIR principles, which can be considered as enablers of the implementation of EOSC: in this case too, the results seem positive.

Indeed, as reported in Figure 5, out of 1251 observations gathered by EOSC-Pillar, EOSC-Nordic¹⁰⁹ and NI4OS-Europe, 31.4% (*ab. val.* 393) of the respondents stated to be "very familiar" with the FAIR principles; 35.1% (*ab. val.* 439) stated to be "familiar", 23.7% (*ab. val.* 297) to be "not very familiar" and 9.7% (*ab. val.* 122) "not familiar at all" with the FAIR principles.

¹⁰⁹ As we mentioned above, in the case of EOSC-Nordic, out of 84 total collected answers referred to a specific country, other 22 collected answers were recorded even though not specifically referred to any country. For this question, it was possible to take into consideration additional 20 records even if not attributed to a specific county. The records added were: 9 records for "very familiar" (93 total records); followed by 9 records for "familiar" (93 total records); and 2 records more for "not familiar at all" (86 total records).

Figure 5: Familiarity with the FAIR principles

The analysis at countries level was carried out only for those countries with 40¹¹⁰ respondents or more, which are: Austria, Belgium, France, Germany, Italy, Slovenia, Serbia, Croatia, Bulgaria, Romania and Moldova. As in the case of the familiarity with EOSC, figure 6 shows that while in Austria, Belgium, France, Germany, Italy and Moldova, the number of respondents familiar with FAIR principles is higher than the number of those who are not, the opposite is true in Slovenia and Romania. In Serbia, Croatia and Bulgaria the respondents are almost evenly split in the two groups.

¹¹⁰ The authors defined the threshold on a question-by-question base, depending on the number of collected observations with the aim of reporting as many information as possible, even if partial.

Figure 6: Familiarity with FAIR principles by country

3.2 EOSC expected benefits

With reference to the perceived benefits of joining EOSC, it has been asked to survey participants if the implementation of EOSC might be beneficial for their organizations. The answers are extremely positive (see Figure 7). Indeed, out of 735 respondents consulted by EOSC-Pillar, EOSC-Nordic, NI4OS-Europe and EOSC-Synergy (only for Portugal), 42.7% (*ab. val.* 314) said that EOSC might be very beneficial, 48.3% (*ab. val.* 355) stated that the implementation of EOSC would be “somewhat” beneficial; 7.6% (*ab. val.* 56) stated that it will be not very much beneficial, and only a small part, 1.4% (*ab. val.* 10) have stated it won’t be beneficial at all¹¹¹. As mentioned in the previous sections, the analysis is based on a non-statistically representative sample and is exploratory in nature but still these results are promising, also considering the facts that there are not significant differences among countries in respect to the perceived benefits of joining EOSC so that the majority of respondents perceive EOSC as beneficial.

¹¹¹ Please note that this question is not present in the EOSC-Synergy reports.

Figure 7: Perceived benefits of EOSC implementation

3.3 Contribution to EOSC

While overall the familiarity with EOSC, with FAIR principles and with the perceived benefits of joining EOSC are arising positively from the analysis, the possible contribution of interviewed organizations to EOSC gives a more complex picture.

It has been asked to the respondents how likely it is that their organisation will contribute to EOSC; this question have been asked only to those that are not already contributing to EOSC. Out of 287 observations from EOSC-Pillar, EOSC-Nordic and EOSC-Synergy (only for Portugal), 242 observations were from EOSC-Pillar¹¹², 20 from EOSC-Nordic and 25 from EOSC-Synergy. As shown in Figure 8, the majority of respondents declare to be able to contribute to EOSC. However, the structure of the sample, which shows an over-representation of the countries surveyed by EOSC-Pillar, suggests reading these results as limited to those countries, which are: Austria, Belgium, Germany, Italy and France.

Having said that, 13.6% (*ab. val.* 39) of the respondents declared that they would contribute to EOSC “very likely”, 67.6% (*ab. val.* 194) will “likely” contribute; 18.1% (*ab. val.* 52) of respondents said that they are “not very likely” to contribute and only the 0.7% (*ab. val.* 2) said they are “not likely at all” to contribute.

¹¹² In this case the target groups addressed by EOSC-Pillar were research infrastructures and universities.

Figure 8: Likelihood to contribute to EOOSC

The team of NI4OS Europe proposed a slightly different question in their survey, asking “How likely will your organization contribute to EOOSC?” indicating five possible areas of contribution: “Funding”, “Manpower”, “Services”, “Content data” and “Consultancy”. Therefore, each respondent was able to provide multiple answers considering the possible options indicated. Results are reported in the figure below.

Figure 9: Likeliness to contribute to OESC by areas of activity

3.4 Engagement with Open Science networks and transnational organisations

Participating in Open Science networks could be seen as an enabler for joining and contributing to EOSC as it testifies that an organisation is active in the field and has the needed competencies to provide input to the Open Science development. At least to a certain extent, the participation of such organisations can be seen as a sign of the maturity of an organisation itself in relation to Open Science principle and practices.

In order to investigate this topic and to understand the organisations' network and their interoperability beyond Open Science it has been asked to the survey participants if they are part of the following organizations: EGI Federation, EUDAT, PRACE or other European organizations (not specified). The total number of respondents for this question is 280 and their answers have been collected by EOSC-Pillar¹¹³, EOSC-Nordic, NI4OS-Europe and EOSC-Synergy (only for the Czech Republic). Out of 280 respondents, 65 respondents declared to be part of EGI Federation; 41 of EUDAT and 27 of PRACE. 77 have stated they are part of other organizations and 70 don't know if their organization is part of one of the mentioned organizations or others (see figure 10).

¹¹³ In this case the number of observations is lower than in other questions because the target group addressed by EOSC-Pillar for this question was e-infrastructures only.

Figure 10: Respondents participation to European OS organizations

Figure 11: Participation to European OS organizations by country

The analysis at country level was carried out on countries with 10¹¹⁴ respondents or more, indeed the number of respondents for this question was considerably lower than previous questions. Figure 11 shows that there is an over-representation of Italian among respondents which, at least partially explains, the results of the previous graph (Figure 10), indeed, 37 of the Italian respondents declared they are part of EGI Federation, 18 of EUDAT, 9 of PRACE and 27 of other organizations not mentioned. Similarity, for other countries, 15 respondents in Germany declared they are part of other organizations. It is worth considering that in Austria, only one respondent declared his organization is part of EGI Federation and one respondent in France part of EUDAT; also, in Czech Republic, only one respondent declared his organization is part of EUDAT and one of PRACE and two of EGI Federation.

The respondents that answered “other”, mentioned the following European or regional organizations:

- OpenAIRE
- CERN
- GÉANT
- CESSDA¹¹⁵, the Consortium of European Social Science Data Archives.
- DARIAH¹¹⁶, a southeast European organization related to “Digital Research Infrastructure for the Arts and Humanities in the Republic of Croatia”.
- EuroHPC¹¹⁷, the leading European supercomputing research network.
- EMBL¹¹⁸, the research network that promotes molecular biology across Europe.
- LUMI¹¹⁹, Large Unified Modern Infrastructure, located in CSC in Finland involving inland, Belgium, Czech Republic, Denmark, Estonia, Iceland, Norway, Poland, Sweden, and Switzerland.
- NORDUnet¹²⁰, a northern European research network, a collaboration between the National Research and Education Networks (NRENs) of the five Nordic countries; Denmark (DeiC), Iceland (RHnet), Norway (Uninett), Sweden (SUNET), and Finland (Funet).

The above-mentioned list of OS organisations is not meant to be exhaustive of course and might not fully represent the situation at country level as it only reflects the respondent’s viewpoints.

Finally, considering the qualitative analysis carried out by the EOSC-Synergy in some of the countries represented in the consortium, it is possible to map some additional information at country level for Slovakia, Portugal, Poland, the United Kingdom and Spain.

In Spain, the Spanish National Research Council (CSIC) is the mandated institution country-wide that coordinates the participation of Spain in EOSC. An important update is that CSIC has been selected by the

¹¹⁴ Each threshold is different because it depends on the minimum of collected answers to be considered for each question.

¹¹⁵CESSDA Members - Slovenia. <https://www.cessda.eu/About/Consortium/CESSDA-Countries/CESSDA-Members/Slovenia> ; RDA in Slovenia. <https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/rda-slovenia>

¹¹⁶DARIAH-HR. <http://dariah.hr/en/home/>

¹¹⁷ EuroHPC. <https://eurohpc-ju.europa.eu/>; EENET. <http://www.eenet.ee/EENet/news>

¹¹⁸ EMBL. <https://www.embl.org/about/missions/>

¹¹⁹ LUMI. <https://www.lumi-supercomputer.eu/>

¹²⁰ NORDUnet. <https://www.nordu.net/content/network>

EOSC Governance Board in July 2020 as one of the four founding members of the EOSC AISBL, and is thus playing a fundamental role in the ramping up of EOSC. Slovakia participates in EGI Federation through the Institute of Informatics, Slovak Academy of Sciences (SAS) and through the Computing Centre of the SAS. Slovakia stakeholders have participated also in PRACE since 2015.

Portugal is involved and participates in several global initiatives including EGI Federation, PRACE, GÉANT, EuroHPC, EUDAT, OpenAIRE, RDA and IBERGRID. Many organisations participate in EOSC related projects.

The Netherlands quite intensively participates in international bodies and consortia, including EuroHPC, GÉANT, PRACE, EGI Federation, E-IRG.

Poland has an ecosystem of computational infrastructure and e-infrastructures including computational resources for modelling, simulation and data analysis. HPC Centres are the members of multiple international organizations including EGI Federation, EUDAT and PRACE. HPC centres and many research institutions are connected to the PIONIER infrastructure. PIONIER offers networking services on the domestic level and manages international links to *e.g.*, GÉANT, it is responsible for the deployment of IdP, but not all research institutions are involved in it.

The UK is involved in many European and international e-infrastructures initiatives including EGI Federation, EUDAT, GÉANT, OpenAIRE, PRACE and RDA.

4 Main services available, access conditions and potentialities of integration in EOSC

In this chapter we provide an overview on the typologies of services offered by the respondent's organisations. Moreover, it intends to provide an overview about who the users are, who access those services and how they access them (*i.e.*, authentication procedures and training availability).

The chapter is based on the respondents representing e-infrastructures and research infrastructures for the survey carried out by EOSC-Pillar, EOSC-Nordic and EOSC-Synergy¹²¹ and from Supporters and OS facilitators considering the questionnaire administered by NI4OS-Europe (see Chapter 3 for definitions). Indeed, the set of questions which results are here reported were not administered to other stakeholders such as funding bodies as they are not service providers. In order to provide detailed and clear information about the categories who replied, in the following paragraphs, for each of the questions it is reported who the respondents are.

4.1 Mapping available services by disciplines

It has been asked to the respondents for which scientific disciplines the organizations they belong to provide services. The question has been asked by EOSC-Pillar and by EOSC-Synergy (only in Portugal and the Czech

¹²¹ Please notice that for EOSC-Synergy, the only countries considered in the analysis are Portugal and Czech Republic addressing both the questions of research infrastructures and e-infrastructures.

Republic) and was directed to research infrastructures and e-infrastructures. EOSC-Nordic asked this question to research infrastructures only.

For this questions, multiple options were possible: indeed, one organisation can offer services to more than a discipline. As reported in figure 12, out of 1332 observations, 29.5% (*ab. val.* 393) indicate service provision for disciplines related to natural science, 17% (*ab. val.* 229) for engineering and technology, 15% (*ab. val.* 198) for medical and health sciences, 14% (*ab. val.* 144) for humanities, 12% (*ab. val.* 157) for social sciences, 11% (*ab. val.* 189) for agricultural science and 2% (*ab. val.* 22) for other disciplines.

Figure 12: Discipline coverage provided by organisations

The figure shows the prevalence of natural sciences, followed by engineering and technology. This gap explains the efforts made by the EC and international Open Science organisations to increase service provision to disciplines other the natural science.

Then, it was asked to survey participants to state what kind of services they offer to the research community choosing among five possible options:

- Knowledge-based resources such as collections, archives or research data;
- data and computing systems, and communication networks;
- major scientific equipment or sets of instruments;
- other research and innovation infrastructures of a unique nature essential to achieving excellence in research and innovation;
- no, none of this list.

Such options are the ones indicated in COUNCIL REGULATION (EC) No 723/2009¹²² and included in the EOSC-Pillar National Initiatives Survey¹²³.

The question was asked by EOSC-Pillar and EOSC-Nordic and by EOSC-Synergy (in Portugal and Czech Republic only). Respondents represent research infrastructure; a total of 536 respondents replied to this question. As shown in figure 13, 32.6% (*ab. val.* 175) of the respondents' state that they offer knowledge-based resources such as collections, archived or research data; 31% (*ab. val.* 166) state they offer major equipment or sets of instruments. Then, 23.3% (*ab. val.* 125) select data and computing systems and communication networks and 10.3% (*ab. val.* 55) select other research and innovation infrastructure. Only 2.8% (*ab. val.* 15) select the option "none of this list".

Figure 13: Services provided to the research community

Therefore, knowledge base resources and scientific equipment are the services most frequently provided to users by research infrastructures.

Considering the qualitative analysis carried out by EOSC-Synergy, the main part of services provided to the research community in the Netherlands is represented by scientific equipment; in the UK, a federated structure provides e-infrastructures facilities including high-performance computing, high-speed networking connectivity, repositories, analytics. In Spain 3% of the research infrastructures in the Map of Unique Scientific and Technical Infrastructures¹²⁴ are from the Knowledge-based resource collection, 7% from Data and computing systems, 55% from the major scientific equipment and 35% from other types.

¹²² Official Journal of the European Union L 206/1, EN 8.8.2009, *COUNCIL REGULATION (EC) No 723/2009*, Article 2 (a); available at <https://eurlex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=OJ:L:2009:206:FULL&from=HR>

¹²³ Bodlos, Anita; Hönegger, Lisa; Kaczmirek, Lars; Beckmann, Volker; Breton, Vincent; Romier, Geneviève; Van Wezel, Jos; Streit, Achim; Stevanovic, Uros; Galeazzi, Fulvio; Tanlongo, Federica; Van Nieuwerburgh, Inge, 2019, "EOSC Pillar "National Initiatives" Survey (SUF edition)", AUSSDA, V1. <https://doi.org/10.11587/VOSVGK>

¹²⁴ ICTS. <https://www.ciencia.gob.es/portal/site/MICINN/ICTS>

In parallel, EOSC-Pillar and EOSC-Nordic and EOSC-Synergy (for Portugal) asked to the e-infrastructures which services they offer in order to cover different definition of research infrastructures ¹²⁵. Total number of respondents is 380. As shown in figure 14, the majority of the respondents 70.3% (*ab. val.* 267) state that they offer infrastructures to store and manage research data; 20.3% (*ab. val.* 77) select the option high-performance computing to process research data; and only 9.5% (*ab. val.* 36) select high-bandwidth networks which transport research data. The definition of these service relies on (European Commission, 2016 adapted by Bodlos et al., 2019).

Figure 14: Specific services provided to the research community

NI4OS-Europe asks information through surveys, but the responses were not sufficient so they carried out a desk research which is reported in project's report (Kosanović and Ševkušić, 2019). Considering the results described there, it is possible to say that for the countries covered by NI4OS-Europe, Data Repositories and Publication Repositories are provided as well as other services: person-to-person consultancy, various types of websites, IT services, library services, repositories, research activities, OS initiatives.

Extrapolating qualitative information from the dedicated reports on countries covered by EOSC-Synergy it is possible to add that also in the Netherlands and in Slovakia e-infrastructures provide mainly knowledge base resources. Those e-infrastructures are organized on networks (the Spanish network of Supercomputing and the IBERGRID network for Distributed Computing). With respect to the research networks, there is one provider (REDIRIS) coordinated with several regional research network centres.

Spain is highly active in distributed computing and supercomputing, both at the level of provisioning of research infrastructures and at platform level, with services to exploit efficiently such resources. For the Data services, Spain is also implementing research repositories through network activities and aggregators that

¹²⁵ EOSC-Pillar and EOSC-Synergy asked this question to the E-Infrastructure, EOSC-Nordic to the research infrastructures.

facilitate the search and access of digital objects. In the Czech Republic, there is only one single e-infrastructure called e-INFRA CZ that is built as a joint effort of CESNET, CERIT-SC and IT4Innovations¹²⁶ and provides a wide variety of services including high-bandwidth networks, high-performance computing, data storage, and AAI.

Finally, in Poland organizations provide the following services: High Performance Computer, cloud storage, archiving (back-ups), networks, PIONER user identity provider.

4.2 Mapping the user communities and the access conditions

Considering now the users targeted by the services, it has been asked to respondents to state who are their users among the seven categories listed below and their frequency of use of offered services:

- researchers based at universities;
- non-university research institutions;
- researchers of private and commercial institutions;
- governmental institutions;
- students;
- citizen scientists;
- professionals;
- others.

EOSC-Nordic and EOSC-Pillar asked this question to e-infrastructures, while EOSC-Synergy (for Czech Republic and Portugal) asked this to research infrastructures and e-infrastructures.

Figure 15, not surprisingly, shows the predominance of researchers (both from university and non) and students as main users, but it also shows that the services are accessible to other user groups too. 57.5% of respondents indicate that researchers based at the universities use their services very frequently and 36.8% that they use they services frequently. 35.6% of respondents indicate students as very frequent users and 45.2% as frequent users. Non-university research institutions are indicated as very frequent user by 38.1% of respondents and frequent users by 41.7% of respondents.

¹²⁶ e-INFRA CZ. <https://www.e-infra.cz/>; CESNET. <https://www.cesnet.cz/>; CERIT-SC. <https://www.cerit-sc.cz/>; IT4Innovations. <https://www.it4i.cz/>

Figure 15: Frequency access to services per user groups

In line to what shown in figure 15, researchers and students are the reported to be the main user groups with higher frequency of access to the services. On the other hand, other categories of users are reported to use the services less frequently; this could be due to various reasons such as lack of technical resources available, lack of awareness of the services or lack of competences. For instance, 30% of representatives of e-infrastructures and research infrastructures report that citizen science communities never access the service and 30.6% that governmental institutions never access their service. This result is relevant as citizen science and governmental institutions could have relevant benefit in using the services offered by EOSC.

With reference to the access conditions (figure 16), it has been asked to survey participants reached by EOSC-Pillar, EOSC-Nordic, NI4OS-Europe and EOSC-Synergy (covering two countries: Czech Republic and Portugal) if they charge users for the services offered. This question has been asked to e-infrastructures by EOSC-Pillar, EOSC-Nordic and to e-infrastructures and research infrastructures by EOSC-Synergy in Czech Republic and Portugal and to the category of Supporters by NI4OS-Europe¹²⁷. As shown in Figure 16, on the total of 208 replies collected, 54.8% (*ab. val.* 114) of the respondents selected “no” while 45.2% (*ab. val.* 94) “yes”.

¹²⁷ This question has been asked only to participants who declared in a previous filtering question that they “acquire own revenues other than funding”

Figure 16: Organisations charging users for services

This result shows a quite balanced situation with a slight majority of respondents who do not charge the users. This could be very much related to policies adopted at national level, but also by single institutions rules. For instance, looking at the response rate per country, (Table 6) it is interesting to notice that Portugal seems to show a higher percentage of access to the services through charge and payments, compared to other countries. Moreover, for some projects this outcome is related only to the infrastructures that declared, in a previous filtering question, that they “acquire own revenues other than funding”. Indeed, as reported in Bodlos et al. (2020, p.50) for countries covered by Pillar “About one third of all e-infrastructures acquire their own revenues other than funding. Of these, about half of the e-infrastructures charge users for some services and only a minority charges users/client for all services. Hence, from a user/client perspective, paying for services is by far rather the exception than the rule.”

Countries	Yes	No
Armenia	0	1
Austria	7	4
Belgium	4	2
Bosnia Herzegovina	1	4
Bulgaria	0	3
Croatia	1	5
Cyprus	1	3
Czech Republic	4	16
Denmark	0	1
Finland	1	0
France	10	6
Georgia	4	0
Germany	9	3
Greece	0	4

Hungary	4	6
Italy	15	10
Moldova	5	13
Montenegro	1	5
North Macedonia	1	11
Portugal	18	2
Romania	2	2
Serbia	3	4
Slovenia	2	9
Sweden	1	0
Total	94	114
%	45.2%	54.8%
Romania	51	3.8%
Serbia	56	4.2%
Slovenia	41	3.1%
Sweden	22	1.6%
Total	1322	100%

Table 6: Charging users for service by country

Considering the data collected from EOSC-Synergy through desk research, it is possible to say that in Slovakia and in Poland organisations don't charge users for services. In Spain the access to the e-infrastructures and scientific repositories is free of charge, even if it doesn't preclude service providers to offer additional services with restricted access to users that reach a specific level of scientific excellence and fulfil ethical requirements.

Different situations exist in the Netherlands and in the UK. In the Netherlands, 5 repositories charge a fee for access, and in 2 cases institutional membership is a requirement. In the UK, charges may be applied for some services, perhaps indirectly rather than directly. According to the UKRI Landscape Analysis infrastructures¹²⁸ in the Social Sciences and Humanities disciplines have truly diverse funding models, much of which is short-term and some charging for data access is observed.

Finally, it has been asked if the organizations plan to authenticate service through an Identity Provider (IdP). The question has been asked by EOSC-Pillar, EOSC-Nordic, NI4OS-Europe and EOSC-Synergy (Czech Republic and Portugal although in this country all responded were "not applicable") and 223 stakeholders replied (Figure 17). EOSC-Pillar, EOSC-Nordic and EOSC-Synergy submitted the question to the e-infrastructures, while NI4OS-Europe has addressed it to the Supporters and Open Science facilitators.

According to the information collected, the number of organisations who plan to authenticate services in less than one year is equal to 12.6% (*ab. val.* 28); the ones who plan to do it in 1 or 2 years is 20.6% (*ab. val.* 46) while 6.3% (*ab. val.* 14) expects to do it in more than 2 years. 18.8% (*ab. val.* 42) states that they do not foresee implementing authentication service, while the remaining 41.7% (*ab. val.* 93) opts for "don't know" or "not applicable".

¹²⁸ UKRI - UK Research and Innovation. (n.d.). *The UK's research and innovation infrastructure: Landscape Analysis*. <https://www.ukri.org/files/infrastructure/landscape-analysis-final-web-version/>

Figure 17: Authentication through Identity Provider (IdP)

Responses are quite scattered, with 33.7% of respondents who plan to implement IdP in the next couple of years. IdP enables service providers to control access to their services from users holding identities (usernames and passwords) from a very broad set of academic, community or social Identity Providers (IdPs), service or dataset that requires authenticated access, enable to track usage at the level of individual users, (i.e., using the EOSC-hub AAI) offering a simple way for user authentication and authorisation. This result suggests a careful reflection in terms of IdP to facilitate its adoptions in the next future but also a deeper investigation in order to understand if other systems are in place already and how to integrate them in EOSC.

Considering the countries analysed by EOSC-Synergy trough desk research, it is possible to add that in the UK most services use either the UK national federation or local authentication. Almost all UK universities are identity providers. In the Netherlands there is no systematic quantitative information, but it is quite possible that repositories are using a variety of methods of authorization and access control. In Slovakia, it is not known if organisations plan to authenticate services through an Identity Provider (IdP).

In Spain authentication appears as an established procedure. In the framework of the federation with Portugal via the initiative IBERGRID, Open ID Connect enabled tools are used. The usage of X.509 certificates is fully supported as well. The Spanish NREN (RedIRIS) provides support to EDUGAIN authentication. Resources based on HPC, such as those of the Spanish Supercomputing Network, or other HPC mainframes, are usually based on local user IDs and passwords. In Poland there is no single uniform identity provider infrastructure. EDUGAIN based solutions are deployed but current infrastructures use their own AA paradigms, usually based on username and password. Some of the Polish infrastructures implement PKI/X.509, but this feature might be disjoint from EDUGAIN. Nowadays, single-sign-on is being deployed within numerous institutions. Some infrastructures implement or integrate functionalities with other ones at the international level.

4.3 A focus on training

In relation to the use of services provided, it has been asked by EOSC-Pillar, EOSC-Nordic and NI4OS-Europe if organizations offer some sort of training to users before to access the services¹²⁹. EOSC-Pillar and EOSC-Nordic addressed the question to the e-infrastructures, while NI4OS-Europe to the Supporters and OS facilitators. A total of 392 organizations replied to this question. Figure 18 shows that 78.8% (*ab. val.* 309) of the respondents offer training, while 21.2% (*ab. val.* 83) doesn't.

Figure 18: Training offered by organizations

This high rate of positive answers shows that training is quite a common practice among the respondents but also for this question, as for others, the sample is strongly influenced by the higher rates of respondents coming from the EOSC-Pillar survey compared to those coming from other projects. Therefore, it is not possible to say that this picture fully represents the situation in countries covered by other regional project even if, made the due consideration, the trend seems positive in all the surveyed countries.

4.4 Towards EOSC-hub integration: Application Programming Interface and Service Level Agreement

APIs enable the EOSC Portal to become a fully interoperable ecosystem of federated Providers and consumers, and further facilitate the composition of Resources on the grounds of commonly agreed service representations and exchange protocols. The open APIs include methods and mechanisms for data acquisition (Resource metadata, indicators, and usage, etc.) from federated catalogues, such that synchronization of content will be seamlessly e-source Catalogue within the EOSC Catalogue and integrate it in their third-party applications.

¹²⁹ EOSC-Synergy doesn't have any questions on training.

Figure 19: EOSC API Functionality

It has been asked to the respondents replying to the survey from EOSC-Pillar and EOSC-Nordic, if the services are accessible by an application programming interface (API). The question has been asked only to e-infrastructures. Must be noted that for this particular question there is an overrepresentation of the countries from EOSC-Pillar, especially Italy, while countries from EOSC-Nordic only represent a small portion of the total. Out of the 225 respondents, 44.4% (*ab. val.* 100) state that this feature is already implemented, 33.8% (*ab. val.* 76) that this feature is currently under development from a theoretical perspective and 21.8% (*ab. val.* 49) say that the feature is already in an implementation phase (Figure 20).

Figure 20: Organisations that provide an application programming interface (API)

Responses suggest that the API implementation is a topic carefully considered by the respondents and for the ones who do not have it yet, procedures are established to be implemented or, at least, respondents are working to implement it from a conceptual point of view. However, as mentioned, it is important to note that the majority of respondents to this and the following questions come from the EOSC-Pillar survey so that the results are mainly referred to the countries covered by this project.

It has been also investigated by EOSC-Pillar, EOSC-Nordic and EOSC-Synergy if the organisations replying to the survey offer Service Level Agreements (SLAs). The question has been made only to the e-infrastructures for EOSC-Pillar and EOSC-Nordic and to the research infrastructures for the by EOSC-Synergy (for Czech Republic and Portugal)¹³⁰. Out of the 338 respondents, 26.7% (*ab. val.* 95) state that SLA are offered for some services, 7% (*ab. val.* 25) for all services and 13.8% (*ab. val.* 49) declare that is foreseen in the near future. On the other hand, 20.8% (*ab. val.* 74) states that SLA are not offered and are not foreseen in the near future. Finally, 26.7% (*ab. val.* 95) selected the option “not applicable” (Figure 21).

¹³⁰ The question was also asked to the Portuguese e-infrastructures. Instead of SLA they refer to SLT (Service Level Targets).

Figure 21: SLAs availability

It seems that the rates of SLA availability for all services and that the percentage of respondents who declare that this is not foreseen in the near future are low. According to the responses collected, major efforts for increasing SLA usage among service providers are needed.

Considering now the countries covered by EOOSC-Synergy through qualitative research, in Spain all service providers in the research infrastructures have to establish some kind of Service Level Agreements (SLAs). In Czech Republic the vast majority of the respondents do not think they can apply SLAs on their services and only few respondents consider offering SLAs in the near future. In Slovakia Service Level Agreements are offered. Organizations participating in a transnational organisation or federation that offers Service Level Agreements (SLAs) or similar contracts are also binding for them. Finally, in the Netherlands SLAs are estimated to be available for a minority of the services offered.

An additional question on SLA, was included aiming to understand if organisations encountered issues or barriers to establish Service Level Agreements (SLAs) with a community (Figure 22). As for the previous one, this question has been asked only to the e-infrastructures for EOOSC-Pillar and EOOSC-Nordic and to the e-infrastructures and the research infrastructures by EOOSC-Synergy (Czech Republic and Portugal). Out of the 117 respondents, 53% (*ab.va.* 62) state they do not encounter barriers, 12.8% (*ab. val.* 15) state “yes” and 34.2% (*ab. val.* 40) selects the option “don’t know”.

Figure 22: Existence of barriers or issues implementing SLAs

Such a high rate of respondents stating that no barriers have been encountered seems a positive result that could motivate also others in implementing such procedures.

Going more into detailed analysis, one question was included in the survey in order to understand what types of Service Level Agreements (SLA) respondents offer or will offer in the future.

As for previous questions related to this topic, the question has been asked only to the e-infrastructures for EOSC-Pillar, EOSC-Nordic and EOSC-Synergy (Portugal) and to the e-infrastructures and research infrastructures for EOSC-Synergy (Czech Republic). Out of the 176 responses collected, the majority (51.7%) (*ab. val.* 91) selected “custom made types”; 20.5% (*ab. val.* 36%) “several predefined types”; 9.1% (*ab. val.* 16) “one fits all type”; 2.3% (*ab. val.* 4) “other types” and 16.5% (*ab. val.* 29) of replies “not applicable”.

Figure 23: Type of SLAs offered

Results show that customized types of SLA are the preferred choice of the majority of respondents.

In addition, EOSC-Pillar and EOSC-Nordic asked, only to e-infrastructures' representatives, which authentication model is used for the service. As shown in Figure 24, out of the 349 responses collected, 44% (*ab. val.* 152) use local authentication, 27% (*ab. val.* 94) are members of a national federation, 22% (*ab. val.* 78) select the option "other", while 4% use model provided by EGI Federation and 3% (*ab. val.* 12) use model provided by EUDAT.

Figure 24: Authentication models for EOSC-Pillar and EOSC-Nordic countries

Local authentication based on password is the most used tool accordingly to respondents. NI4OS-Europe asked a similar question made for the categories of Supporters and OS facilitators. Replies option are slightly different from the one provided by the other projects. However, as shown in Figure 25, results are in line with what emerges from EOSC-Pillar and EOSC-Nordic’ surveys. The majority of respondents, 55.1% (*ab. val.* 54) use a local authentication, 16.3% (*ab. val.* 16) are members of a national federation, 15.3% (*ab. val.* 15) use EOSC provider eduGAIN and 13.3% (*ab. val.* 13) selected the option “other”.

Figure 25: Authentication models for the NI4OS-Europe countries

Also, for the NI4OS-Europe countries, local authentication is the most used model.

5 Policies and procedures for service provision

This chapter reports on the main policies established by the interviewed stakeholders or publicly available policies, for service provision and/ or technical barriers that limit the development of policies and regulations for service provisions.

5.1 Policy and regulatory procedure

Survey participants were asked if their organisation developed informal or formal regulations related to their work processes, addressing certain aspects related to Open Science services which are:

- Research data management (RDM)
- Open research data
- Long-term availability of research data
- Compliance of data to the FAIR principles
- Publication of data in a repository
- Publication of data in a certified repository
- Other

Data on this was collected only by EOSC-Pillar and EOSC-Nordic projects. The target groups addressed for this question were research infrastructures, e-infrastructures and universities. There is some qualitative information available for some other countries collected by the EOSC-Synergy project that will be reported too.

Figure 26: Policies and regulation availability

For “no regulation” the values are ranging from 20% up to 30% with only a spike to 36% (*ab. val.* 122) for “publication of data in a certified repository”. The same applies for “informal regulation” where the values range from 20 up to 32% with a spike of 36% (*ab. val.* 211) for “Compliance of data to the FAIR principles”. Despite the high values registered in terms of knowledge of FAIR principles (see paragraph 4.1) the presence of formal or informal policies on this aspect is still on-going in many of the respondent’s organisations.

Regarding “formal regulation” (ranging from 11% and 24%) and “Publicly available policy” (ranging from 13% to 20%) the topics that emerged as most regulated are “Research data management” (25%) (*ab. val.* 131) and “publication of data in a repository” (24%) (*ab. val.* 140).

Most of the data presented in the previous paragraph are related to the countries surveyed by EOSC-Pillar and for a minority of cases by EOSC-Nordic; for some other countries the results of the question were given in a qualitative form thanks to the research work carried out by EOSC-Synergy.

Currently, in Slovakia there is not an official policy on FAIR data at national level, but it will be implemented in the next future. The situation is similar in the Czech Republic – the FAIR data policy on national level is missing, however, there are currently activities among academic institutions on establishing working groups for research data policy development. There are also increasing negotiations with the Czech government aiming at establishing an official policy for research data with emphasis on FAIR principles.

In the United Kingdom the strategic-level responsibility for policy making on Open Science and FAIR data is mainly managed by the UKRI (United Kingdom Research and Innovation organization) that acts in

consultation with stakeholders such as universities and with BEIS (the Department for Business, Energy and Industrial Strategy).

In the Netherlands, the FAIR data policy has started to gain popularity among policy makers, and it is usually required that data comply with these principles. Usually, the default access is open, but there might be restrictions to openness on various grounds, especially on legal grounds, such as the protection of personal data in the compliance with the GDPR.

In Poland the compliance of data to the FAIR principles is considered; indeed, amongst the basic rules for awarding public contracts there is the principle of FAIR competition. In Spain, the new Strategy of Science, Technology and Innovation 2021–2027 explicitly mentions the objectives and the 14th Actuation Axis the promotion of the production of FAIR data and the support to the Spanish contribution to the EOSC¹³¹.

Moreover, the organizations were asked to provide information about whether they limit the access to their services to some user groups and in that case to which group.

In total 647 answers were collected from EOSC-Pillar, EOSC-Nordic and NI4OS-Europe surveys and their results are shown in Figure 27; some other answers were collected by EOSC-Synergy in the Portuguese survey and in a qualitative format and will be reported below.

The groups of users taken in consideration for the restrictions are: General public (no access restriction), National users, Users or communities approved by the funding body (e.g., due to regional or research topic restrictions), Users selected by competition, Members of certain communities or organisations (e.g., virtual organisations), Not applicable, Other.

Only one answer was allowed per respondent, meaning that the organization restricts their services only to the selected category (*i.e.*, if select “national users” it means that they only offer services to them).

¹³¹ EOSC Synergy – Spain. <https://www.eosc-synergy.eu/europe/spain/>

Figure 27: Restrictions on services

The figure shows that 32.3% (*ab. val.* 209) of respondents do not restrict the access to their services to anyone but allows everyone to use them, next with 22.4% (*ab. val.* 145) there are the organizations that do restrict their access only to Members of certain communities or organisations. The other less common values in order are: Users or communities approved by the funding body with 15% (*ab. val.* 97), Other with 11.1% (*ab. val.* 72), National users with 6.8% (*ab. val.* 44) and finally Users selected by competition 7.4% (*ab. val.* 48). Only 4.9% (*ab. val.* 32) of the respondents find the answer of the question not applicable to their methods ¹³².

Regarding the countries of the EOSC-Synergy analysis it is possible to say that, in Czech Republic roughly 40% of stakeholders do not apply any restrictions whatsoever meanwhile others restrict their access to some groups but with smaller percentages.

In the Netherlands, especially for repositories, there are a variety of access licences, differentiating between open and restricted access licences, and, less frequently, they also contain data that is closed to external access or where access is embargoed.

In Slovakia many organisations provide services only to national users due to the national funding (structural funds) since they cannot generate income from their infrastructure.

In the UK, access to data services and resources is broadly determined by funding source. Services or other resources developed using national funding may only be available nationally whereas resources developed by an institution from its own budget will be provided for its own researchers. Access to unlimited resources is usually open, whereas limited resources generally have a competitive allocation mechanism applied to them.

¹³² For more information on this topic: Hammargren et al. (2020). *D2.1: Open science policies and resource provisioning in the Nordic and Baltic countries (first report)*; Fischer et al. (2020b). *D2.4: The EOSC Delivery Chain*; Fischer et al. (2020a). *D2.3: Open Science in the Nordics: Legal Insights*.

Next, organizations were asked about the existence of any kind of procedural/technical barriers that could limit the expansion of their services to other user groups.

For this question 392 answers were collected from the surveys of EOSC-Pillar, EOSC-Nordic and NI4OS-Europe and are reported in Figure 28, some other answers were collected by EOSC-Synergy (however, questions to research infrastructures and e-infrastructures were included in the Portuguese survey and landscape report) in a qualitative format and will be reported below. The options were “Yes”, “No” “Don’t know”.

Figure 28: Existence of policies/barrier that limit the expansion of the services

The result is really positive, the majority of the organizations interviewed (52.6%) (*ab. val.* 179) appear to have no problems in expanding their services and user base in the future.

In Czech Republic roughly half of the respondents are aware of the presence of barriers (41.6%) for expansion but are working to remove them.

6 Funding, sustainability and business models

This chapter is dedicated to funding strategies and business models related to the Open Science community and in particular it includes details on main funding received or offered by the interviewed stakeholders.

It also reports on the presence of a long-term planning strategy for funding of infrastructures (in this document defined as “roadmap”) and if this roadmap belongs to collective projects (i.e., European, national...) or if it is custom made by the single organization.

6.1 Sustainability strategies: funding and revenue models for service providers

This paragraph will address the following questions:

- Who recurrently provides funding to your organisation?
- What are the sources of your own revenues other than funding?

For both questions the answers were provided by e-infrastructures from the surveys submitted by EOSC-Pillar, EOSC-Nordic and NI4OS-Europe and by research infrastructures and e-infrastructures in the survey carried out by EOSC-Synergy in Portugal; results are reported in Figure 29. EOSC-Synergy collected qualitative information on some of their countries too and related results are here after reported.

Respondents were asked to select the type of funders from a list (more than one option could be selected). The options were: Research institutions, University, State/Ministry, Region/Town, Research communities, European funds, Industry/ small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs), Funding agencies/Funding bodies, Other.

Figure 29: Who provides funds to the organizations

The two most common answers of the survey are State/Ministry with 35.1% (*ab. val.* 327) of responses and European funds with 29.2% (*ab. val.* 272). Less common were Research communities with 5.9% (*ab. val.* 55) and Industry/ SMEs with 7.4% (*ab. val.* 69).

The results show how the two biggest funders for the Open Science organizations are State/ministries and EU funds, which are indeed the main actors of the European research landscape.

Considering the information collected by EOSC-Synergy, in Czech Republic the majority of the Open Science organizations are funded by State/Ministry and by European funds and funding agencies/bodies.

In Spain the main sources for funding of research infrastructures are through competitive processes involving external evaluation agencies. Depending on the geographical level there are different types of funding given. At the regional dimension, the governments of the regions opened research grants mainly leveraging on European Regional Development Funds (ERDF); at national level, the State Plan of Scientific and Technical Research (2017-2020)¹³³ and Spanish Roadmap for the ERA Development 2016- 2020 provided a budget of 257M€ for financing related organisations; moreover, there is a strong participation in calls of the H2020 European research framework programme.

In the Netherlands, the great majority of the RIs is funded by the state, first of all by the Ministry of Education Culture and Science (OCW), but other Ministries also fund certain RIs.

In Slovakia organizations are mainly funded by state (Ministry), European funds, funding agencies/funding bodies while other funding possibilities like research institution(s), university, region/town, research communities, industry/ SMEs) are generally not available. Most organizations acquire other revenues via consultancy or training, other possibilities related to online services provision (software as a service, applications, storage, computing), and hosting (hardware and services for third parties) are less used.

More details have been gathered by exploring if public funding is the unique form of income for respondents or if there are other sources of revenues. Information on this topic was collected by EOSC-Pillar, EOSC-Nordic and NI4OS-Europe, and by EOSC-Synergy for Czech Republic and Portugal while other qualitative information shown below were provided for the other countries investigated by EOSC-Synergy.

Two questions were made on this topic: the first question was answered by 817 respondents, and results are shown in Figure 30, while the second was answered by 303 (the number of organizations that gave a positive answer to the first question) and results are shown in Figure 31.

¹³³ State Plan of Scientific and Technical Research (2017-2020).

https://www.ciencia.gob.es/portal/site/MICINN/menuitem.29451c2ac1391f1febebed1001432ea0/?vgnnextoid=bcd9c5e1876f5610VgnVCM1000001d04140aRCRD&lang_chosen=en

Figure 30: Presence of revenues other than funding

Only 29.5% (*ab. val.* 129) of the total respondents declare to have revenues other than funding; the vast majority (70.5%) (*ab. val.* 576) rely on funding.

In Czech Republic most organizations don't acquire funding in other ways (67%) than through public funding. In the Netherlands it is rare for an organization to be funded by only one channel, but there isn't enough detailed information about it. It's believed to be mostly through temporary projects, or subscriptions.

As already stated before, the data for the second question was collected among the organizations that answered "Yes" to the first one, and the respondents were asked to choose among four different types of extra income (Online services, Hosting, Consultancy, Other) with a multiple-choice format.

Figure 31: Other sources of revenues

The results of the figure are clear: more than one third of the organizations rely on consultancy (35.6%) (*ab. val.* 108) to increase their revenues, some have revenues from online services provision (21.1%) (*ab. val.* 64), while hosting (15.8%) (*ab. val.* 48) is the less commonly used option. 27.4% of respondents answered “other” (*ab. val.* 83), many of them specified that they use some kind of paid subscriptions.

6.2 Procurement Models

It has also been asked to the organizations participating in the survey made by EOSC-Pillar, EOSC-Nordic and two countries from EOSC-Synergy (Portugal and Czech Republic) how they buy supplies, resources or services. In particular, EOSC-Pillar and EOSC-Nordic asked this question to e-infrastructures, while the countries from EOSC-Synergy submitted the question to the following categories: in Portugal to research infrastructures and to the e-infrastructures, while Czech Republic to research infrastructures only. As shown in Figure 32, based on the total of 423 respondents, 55.6% (*ab. val.* 235) buy or rent what they need through a dedicated tender, 24.6% (*ab. val.* 104) use pre-negotiated procurement or tender, 15.1% (*ab. val.* 64) buy or rent without a tender, while 4.7% (*ab. val.* 20) use “other” means.

Figure 32: Procurement Models

It is not a surprise that for most of the respondents the acquisition should be regulated by a tender, as this is a procedure connected to national and European laws. Indeed, also considering the countries covered by EOOSC-Synergy it is possible to add that in all the countries the rules for procurements are regulated by the law. In Slovakia organizations buy or rent supplies, resources or services with tender, or with pre-negotiated procurement/tender. In Poland, the supply is regulated by the Polish law, from March 2, 2004 to December 31, 2020, the rules for awarding public procurement are specified in the Act of January 29, 2004, Public Procurement Law. In particular, entities of the public finance sector are obliged to apply the provisions on public procurement, as well as, among others other entities of a similar nature or controlled in a specific way by public finance sector entities, if they purchase supplies, works or services. Orders can be awarded in eight modes described in the Act: unlimited tender, restricted tender, negotiations with the announcement, competitive dialogue, negotiations without announcement, single-source orders, price inquiries, electronic bidding.

In Spain Procurement of services and resources is mainly constrained to the obligations of the Spanish Law of Contracts for the Public Sector. In this sense, services or resources below 15.000 € (taxes excluded) can be exceptionally contracted without the need of a tender. For any service or resource contract above such limit, a public tender is required. Public tenders are usually base on an objective evaluation based on quantitative criteria plus an expert evaluation by a committee.

Most procurement in the UK is currently governed by EU treaty principles and Directives and the UK regulations which implement them. The UK's departure from the EU may result in some changes in future. Jisc¹³⁴ offers a data archiving framework to all organisations connected to its Janet network, through a framework based on an EU procurement. Jisc also participates in the GÉANT IaaS framework which offers cloud infrastructure as a service.

Dutch public procurement law recognises the general principles of public procurement law (equal treatment, non-discrimination, mutual recognition, proportionality and transparency) and the general principles of

¹³⁴ Jisc. <https://www.jisc.ac.uk/>

Dutch civil law (including pre-contractual good faith). The Proportionality Guide further elaborates on the principle of proportionality and how it should be applied in procurement procedures. Accordingly, the application of the Guide should strengthen the position of small and medium-sized enterprises during tender procedures. Contracting authorities may only deviate from the detailed provisions on proportionality if this is properly motivated in the tender documents.

Considering now the countries covered by NI4OS-Europe the project has structured a similar question to investigate how OS facilitators and Supporters, acquire services or other supplies. The question provided three options for the reply: i) buy, ii) buy or rent on pre-negotiated procurement/tender and iii) other.

As shown in Figure 33, out of the total of 93 of facilitators and supporters replying to the question, 71% (*ab. val.* 66) select “other”, 17.2% (*ab. val.* 16) select “buy” and 11.8% (*ab. val.* 11) select the pre-negotiated procurement or tender.

Figure 33: How NI4OS-Europe organizations buy supplies, services or resources

It is worth to notice that in the field “other”, most of the respondents have specified they buy supplies, services or resources with the procurement procedure.

6.3 The point of view of funding bodies

This paragraph focuses on funding bodies and reflects on what they fund and if they have any roadmap for supporting the OS infrastructures for the future.

First question asked was on the kind of activities are the funding bodies providing support to, the options provided were seven:

- Human Resources (HR)
- Projects
- Hardware
- Software
- Operations

- Infrastructures
- Others.

Multiple answers were allowed, and 4788 observations were collected by EOOSC-Pillar, EOOSC-Nordic and NI4OS-Europe; the results are shown in Figure 34, some additional qualitative information was provided by EOOSC-Synergy.

It must be mentioned that most of the observations reported in the graph below come from the countries covered by NI4OS-Europe (*ab. val.* 4025). EOOSC-Nordic collected fewer responses (*ab. val.* 588), but the answers may be considered as representative because the public funding agencies are few in the represented countries and are well represented in the gathered data. With reference to EOOSC-Pillar the number of collected answers of funding bodies (*ab. val.* 175) is representatives of all the countries object of Pillar analysis.

Figure 34: Activities funded

From the figure it emerges how “Projects” is the most funded activity (69.9%) (*ab. val.* 478), followed by HR (48.2%) (*ab. va.* 330), Infrastructures (39.8%) (*ab. val.* 272) and Software (35.4%) (*ab. val.* 242) are almost at the same level, while Hardware (28.8%) (*ab. val.* 197) and Operations (26.6%) (*ab. val.* 182) are the less common options. Only 7.3% (*ab. val.* .50) of the total gives funding to other activities.

Considering the countries analysed by EOOSC-Synergy, it is possible to say that in Czech Republic most of the organizations fund operations, infrastructure and Human resources. In Spain, all the categories are supported but in different types of actions. Most calls for research infrastructure funding do not include Human Resources as eligible costs. However, funding in Spain comes at national, regional and local level, which provides a wide range of options to complement funding.

Finally, it was asked about the existence of a roadmap for infrastructures and in case of a positive response, if the roadmap is aligned with some kind of strategy (European or national). EOSC-Pillar, EOSC-Nordic and NI4OS-Europe considered together collected a total of 684 answers and the results are shown in Figure 35. The second aspect, the alignment of the roadmap with European or national strategies, got a lower number of responses (33) as it was only asked to those who declared to have a roadmap in the previous question (see Figure 36).

Figure 35: Existence of a roadmap

Results show that the majority of the interviewed funding bodies actually have a roadmap for supporting research infrastructures (40.8%, *ab. val.* 279), 27.8% (*ab. val.* 190) don't know if their organizations have it or not, while 31.4% (*ab. val.* 215) don't have it.

Figure 36: Type of roadmap

For the organizations that do have a roadmap, 30.3% follow a European one, 24.2% a national one and 45.5%, the highest value of the sample, have a personal one.

Considering now the additional information gathered via qualitative analysis by EOSC-Synergy, in Slovakia there is a national roadmap that covers 5 years. In Spain there are specific funding lines for the long-term support of Unique infrastructures and specific programs by disciplines. In Czech Republic only one funding organization is aligning its roadmap to the national roadmap. A UK national research and innovation infrastructure roadmap was published in November 2019. Foundation for Science and Technology (FCT), the Portuguese public funding agency that supports science, technology and innovation, in all scientific domains, launched in 2013 a call for the creation of the Portuguese Roadmap of research infrastructures of Strategic Interest. This brought Portugal into the group of European countries, which have produced their national roadmaps, in alignment with ESFRI. In 2014, forty research infrastructures were integrated in this roadmap. Just recently, it was published the 2020 Update of the National Roadmap of research infrastructures, that includes fifty-six research infrastructures.

7 Conclusions

This report presents a secondary analysis of the data and information gathered by four regional EU projects (EOSC-Pillar, NI4OS-Europe, EOSC-Nordic and EOSC-Synergy) and complements the long-term monitoring of EOSC landscape.

The nature of this research is exploratory and descriptive: it provides information useful to the EOSC governance and the European Commission to better design and implement the future actions for the fulfilment of EOSC agenda, but it needs to be considered together with other analysis undergoing such as those of the EOSC landscaping working group (EC; 2020) and the analysis of the four regional projects¹³⁵.

It is important to stress that the report is based on a non-statistically representative sample and that results have to be treated accordingly.

On average 51,5% of the survey's respondents are familiar with EOSC even if differences among countries are significant. The majority of respondents consider it as likely beneficial for their organisation. However, the capability to contribute to EOSC differs from country to country with countries such as Italy, Austria, Belgium, Germany and France more likely to contribute than others such as Moldova, Serbia and North Macedonia which started to develop Open Science policies more recently.

Considering the Open Science services represented by the respondents, there is a prevalence of services targeting natural sciences, followed by engineering and technology while all other disciplines are less represented, at least in terms of service provision.

Researchers (both from university and non) and students are the main users of research infrastructure and e-infrastructure services, but access is granted to other user groups in the majority of cases. The great majority of service providers participating in the surveys (78.8%) offer training to their users.

The sustainability model of the vast majority of research infrastructures and e-infrastructure is based on public funding which is granted in most cases by governmental and European funds (33% of responses and 26.5% of respondents respectively). Nevertheless, approximately 30% of respondents declare to access other sources of funding among which consultancy service provision and online services' offering.

In some countries the actual convergence towards EOSC at technical and policy/regulation level appear facilitated by the presence of standardised working regulations and technical solutions such as the availability of Open API's and Legal Service Agreements (LSAs).

As said this report complements other analysis and offers its contribution towards a better understanding of the state of the art of the OS community in Europe in terms of service provision, regulations and sustainability models. It wishes to offer an overview and contribute to the ongoing work in the realisation of EOSC as a space to support EU science.

¹³⁵ Hammargren, P. et al. (2020); Fischer, L. et al (2020a); Fischer, L. et al (2020b). *D2.4: The EOSC Delivery Chain.*; Bodlos, A. et al. (2020); Kosanović, B. & Ševkušić, M. (2019); Pereira, F. (2020); Dobrucký, M., Hluchy, L. (2020); Blanquer, I. et al. (2020)

References

- Ayris P., Berthou, J.Y., B., Bruce, R., Lindstaedt, S., Monreale, A., Mons, B., Murayama, Y., Södergård, C., Tochtermann, K., Wilkinson R. (2016). *First report and recommendations of the Commission High Level Expert Group on the European Open Science Cloud*. <https://ec.europa.eu/digital-single-market/en/news/first-report-high-level-expert-group-european-open-science-cloud>.
- Blanquer, I., Campos, I., Cuesta Ruíz, M., Figueroa Rojas, I. (2020). *EOSC-SYNERGY Landscaping Country Report for Spain*. <https://doi.org/10.20350/digitalCSIC/12624>
- Bodlos, A., Hönegger, L., Kaczmirek, L., Beckmann, V., Breton, V., Geneviève, R., van Wezel, J., Streit, A., Stevanovic, U., Galeazzi, F., Tanlongo, F., van Nieuwerburgh, I. (2019). *Questionnaire for the EOSC-Pillar "National Initiatives" Survey*. Vienna: AUSSDA. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.11587/VOSVGK>.
- Bodlos, A., Hönegger, L., Kaczmirek, L., Beckmann, V., Breton, V., Romier, G., van Wezel, J., Streit, A., Stevanovic, U., Galeazzi, F., Tanlongo, F., Van Nieuwerburgh, I. (2020). *EOSC-Pillar D3.1 Summary report of the EOSC-Pillar National Initiatives Survey*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3937317>
- Budroni, P., Burgelman, J.C., Schoupe, M. (2019). *Architectures of Knowledge: The European Open Science Cloud*. ABI Technik, 39 (2),130-141. <https://doi.org/10.1515/abitech-2019-2006>
- Dobrucký, M., Hluchy, L. (2020). *EOSC-SYNERGY, Landscaping Report Country Slovakia*. <https://doi.org/10.20350/digitalCSIC/12626>
- Doorn, dr. P.K. Data Archiving and Networked Services (DANS-KNAW). (2020). *EOSC-SYNERGY Landscaping Country Report the Netherlands*. DANS. <https://doi.org/10.17026/dans-2by-ereu>
- European Commission. (2020). *Landscape of EOSC-related infrastructures and initiatives. Report from the EOSC executive board working group (WG) landscape: version 2*. <https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/9c7f3c1e-2aea-11eb-9d7e-01aa75ed71a1/language-en/format-PDF/source-173604556>
- European Commission. (2016). *European Cloud Initiative - Building a competitive data and knowledge economy in Europe*. <https://ec.europa.eu/transparency/regdoc/rep/1/2016/EN/1-2016-178-EN-2-1.PDF>
- European Commission. (2016). *Realising the European Open Science Cloud - First report and recommendations of the Commission High Level Expert Group on the European Open Science Cloud*. Luxembourg: Publications Office of the European Union. <https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/2ec2eced-9ac5-11e6-868c-01aa75ed71a1>
- European Commission. (2015). *Validation of the results of the public consultation on Science 2.0: Science in Transition*. <https://ec.europa.eu/digital-single-market/en/news/final-report-science-20-public-consultation>

European Commission. (2009). Official Journal of the European Union L 206/1. EN 8.8.2009. *COUNCIL REGULATION (EC) No 723/2009*. Article 2 (a). <https://eurlex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=OJ:L:2009:206:FULL&from=HR>

Fischer, L., Hammargren, P.O., Iozzi, F., Kontkanen, P., Rasmussen, T. (2020a). *D2.3: Open Science in the Nordics: Legal Insights*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4147409>

Fischer, L., Hammargren, P.O., Riungu-Kalliosaari, L., Arvola, M. (2020b). *D2.4: The EOSC Delivery Chain*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4264121>

Hammargren, P.O., Arvola, M., Rauste, P. (2020). *Open science policies and resource provisioning in the Nordic and Baltic countries (first report)*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4083762>

Kosanović, B., Ševkušić, M. (2019). *D2.1. Stakeholder map, inventory, policy matrix*. <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3736129>

Kupczyk, M. (2020). *EOSC-SYNERGY Landscaping Country Report Poland*. <https://doi.org/10.20350/digitalCSIC/12625>

Robertson, D. (2020). *EOSC-Synergy: Landscaping Country Report United Kingdom*. <https://doi.org/10.20350/digitalCSIC/12631>

Růžička, M., Křenková, I., Matyska, L. (2020). *EOSC-Synergy Landscaping Country Report: The Czech Republic (Version 2020-05-28)*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3891370>

Pereira, F. (2020). *EOSC-SYNERGY Landscaping Country Report Portugal*. https://doi.org/10.34642/fccn_bep7-qk29

Other sources

EOSC-Pillar. <https://www.eosc-pillar.eu/>

EOSC-Nordic. <https://www.eosc-nordic.eu/>

EOSC Synergy. <https://www.eosc-synergy.eu/>

NI4OS-Europe. <https://ni4os.eu/>

Jisc. <https://www.jisc.ac.uk/#>

UKRI. <https://www.ukri.org/files/infrastructure/landscape-analysis-final-web-version/>

DataDOI. <https://datadoi.ee/>

NORDUnet. <https://www.nordu.net/>

NeIC. <https://neic.no/nt1/>

WLCG. <https://wlcg.web.cern.ch/>

Kielipankki. <https://www.kielipankki.fi/>

Uninett. <https://www.uninett.no/en>

ICTS. <https://www.ciencia.gob.es/portal/site/MICINN/ICTS>

CESSDA. <https://www.cessda.eu/>

RDA. <https://www.rd-alliance.org/>

DARIA-HR. <http://dariah.hr/en/home/>

EuroHPC Joint Undertaking. <https://eurohpc-ju.europa.eu/>

EENET. <http://www.eenet.ee/EENet/news>

EMBL. <https://www.embl.org/about/missions/>

LUMI. <https://www.lumi-supercomputer.eu/>

EOSCPilot. <https://eoscpilot.eu/>

Eurostat Data Browser.

https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/demo_urespop/default/table?lang=en

Agency for Statistics of Bosnia and Herzegovina. <http://www.bhas.ba>

European Commission. (2015). *Validation of the results of the public consultation on Science 2.0: Science in Transition*. <https://ec.europa.eu/digital-single-market/en/news/final-report-science-20-public-consultation>

Juncker, J. (27 October 2015). *Construire l'Europe industrielle du numérique*. Speech.

https://ec.europa.eu/commission/presscorner/detail/fr/SPEECH_15_5938

